

Project Management Practices and implementation of shared Core
Banking System in Ethiopia

A Case of Selected Member Microfinance Institutions of Association
of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions (AEMFI)

A Research Proposal Submitted to the Faculty of Business Administration and
Management in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Award of Master Art in
Microfinance Management

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this study titled “**Project Management Practices and implementation of shared Core Banking System in Ethiopia a Case of Selected Member Microfinance Institutions of AEMFI**” is my own work and it has not been submitted at any university for any award.

Signature:

Date: 04/02/2025

Addis Admas Lakew

APPROVAL

This is to certify that this research report titled “**Project Management Practices and implementation of shared Core Banking System in Ethiopia a Case of Selected Member Microfinance Institutions of AEMFI**” has been under my supervision and it is now ready for examination.

Signature

Date.....11/02/2025.....

Mr. Edward Katumba Segawa

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to Meklit Microfinance Institution Share Company.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AEMFI:	Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions
Br net	Bankers Realm Network
CVI	Content Validity Index
IT	Information Technology
NBE:	National Bank of Ethiopia
IFAD:	International fund for Agricultural Development
MFI:	Microfinance Institutions
US:	United States
IV:	Independent Variables
DV:	Dependent Variables
MV:	Moderating Variables
CEO:	Chief Executive Officer
MIS:	Management Information System

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at examining project management practices and the implementation of core banking system project in selected Microfinance institutions in Ethiopia under the Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institution. Specifically, it investigates three key project management practices: assess effect of stakeholder management, evaluate effect of monitoring and evaluation, and examine the effect of risk management on the implementation of the core banking system project.

The research conducted utilized a cross sectional study design. A quantitative research approach was utilized. Data were gathered through a questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale, administered by taking sample size of 92 selected participants, including project managers, project team members, Office experts and Customer Service officer from the selected Microfinance institutions. The analysis was done using SPSS to generation descriptive as well as inferential statistics. The analysis focused on three project management practices: stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management. The regression analysis results indicated that stakeholder management (Pearson correlation= 0.773), risk management (Pearson correlation= 0.773), and project monitoring and evaluation (Pearson correlation= 0.870) were strongly associated with the successful implementation of the core banking system. This suggests that changes in stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation and risk management correspondingly influence changes in implementation of core banking system. The combined effect of the independent variables accounted for 77 percent of the variation in core banking system implementation, highlighting the necessity of considering these factors to enhance core banking system project outcomes in the Microfinance institution sector. The study recommends that management should participate stakeholder's involvement beginning from initial stage by assigning its roles and the management of each MFI should carefully identify potential risks throughout the project lifecycle and devise suitable mitigation strategies. Additionally, the MFI's management should improve its monitoring and evaluation strategies to support the success of core banking system implementation.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The study intended to assess Project management practices and how they affect the implementation of the core banking system of selected member microfinance institutions of AEMFI.

This study used project management practices as the independent variable, which includes stakeholder management, project monitoring and evaluation, and risk management as indicators. The dependent variable, on the other hand, was the implementation of the core banking system, with indicators of banking timeliness, cost-effectiveness, and customer satisfaction.

This section provided an overview of the study, including its introduction, background of the study, the problem being addressed, the objectives and the hypothesis, the scope of the study and justification of the study. It also included an explanation for why the research is essential and significant as well as a conceptual framework, key term definitions and conclusion.

1.1. Background of the study

Project Management Institute (2017) defined projects as a short-term assignment aimed at producing an exclusive product or service, necessitating competent utilization of resources. Essentially, projects involve cohorts working together towards a mutual objective, with the intent of achieving the specified targets on schedule, within budget, and up to the agreed-upon level of quality. The tasks executed by these individuals are frequently intertwined.

Project management practice involves arranging, coordinating, overseeing, and regulating every component of a project, while motivating everyone involved to work towards the project's objectives in a safe manner, within previously established

schedules, budgets, and performance standards. From this definition, it becomes apparent that project management centers on project performance, specifically in terms of short-term triumphs, such as following pre-set criteria related to time, cost, and quality (Radujković & Sjekavica, 2017).

A project is a collection of work tasks that are connected and supervised by a project manager. The goal of the project is to meet certain objectives within a given timeframe (Franklin, 2019).

Financial institutions today are facing a new challenge. They are no longer competing solely based on the quality of their services. These days, customers' expectations have increased, and in order to meet these ever-changing needs, it is necessary for modern microfinance institutions to predict developments before they happen. Additionally, they must focus on keeping operating costs low while continually improving productivity. Therefore, a robust IT infrastructure is essential for success (Cherif et al., 2021). Modernization of Microfinance Institutions is crucial for a country's economic progress, as it enables them to grow and contribute further. To stay relevant and meet the demands of various customer segments, MFIs have to offer more products and increase their channel, which makes multi-channel service delivery. Thus, Implementing core banking systems is essential to handle the rising number of transactions and payments (Afrianto et al., 2016).

The shared infrastructure system in a Microfinance Institution is the foundation upon which all member microfinance institutions can share resources. It can be viewed as the central component of the institution's IT platform. Due to technological advancements, the core system now encompasses a broader range of functions, making it a comprehensive solution for various business lines. The core banking system is located in the Associations data center and serves as the central operational database for customer assets and liabilities. It also enables a complete overview of a customer's interactions with the Microfinance Institution (Rahman & Qi, 2016)

The ways in which projects are executed can be different for each company and even change for different projects within the same company. The existing literature has provided evidence that there has been a significant increase in the demand and adoption of project management practices within the business industry over the past two decades (Brookes et al., 2014).

While project type and extent are capable of indicating the most effective methodologies for executing a project, selecting the appropriate methodology can be intimidating for project teams (Control et al., 2008). Research indicates that if there are no established protocols or methods in place, the probability of successfully completing a project within the planned timeline, achieving all intended objectives, and staying within budget is considerably lower than the likelihood of encountering issues in any of these areas or even giving up on the project entirely (Brookes et al., 2014)

According to (Brookes et al., 2014) the recommended practices for effective implementation include acknowledging the complexity of the project environment, choosing a project that will provide the most benefit to the target audience, identifying appropriate implementation strategies, aligning organizational processes with the project, and ensuring robust program and project management for successful implementation.

(Abdul-Hanan & Abdul-Rasheed, 2015) states that the implementation of projects, particularly in the field of information technology, has had a significant impact on the progress and advancement of the banking industry.

In the past few years, there have been new developments in the Ethiopian Microfinance Institution industry that have prompted these institutions to recognize the importance of undergoing a core-banking transformation. This transformation is necessary to address both internal needs such as growth and efficiency as well as external factors like regulations and competition (Afrianto et al., 2016). Thus, it is

essential to implement the core banking system in the financial sector of Ethiopia to foster the growth and progress of Microfinance Institutions within the nation.

In regard to this, the Association of Ethiopian Microfinance (AEMFI) has started adopting shared Core banking system for its member Microfinance institutions on May, 2017. The Core banking system procurement by AEMFI was signed with an international technology vendor based in Kenya called Craft Silicon (Capital, 2017).

Microfinance institutions are experiencing rising competition from fresh players in the industry, including online and direct banking institutions that rely on modern core banking systems. Microfinance institutions have shifted their focus and are now more customer-oriented. They are placing importance on providing good customer service, having a comprehensive understanding of their customers, and using automated system strategies that are based on building strong relationships (Al Ali, 2021).

For this reason, microfinance institutions are initiated to implement shared core banking systems to ensure excellence in customer service delivery (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) and in Ethiopia two dozen microfinance institutions (MFIs) have deployed a shared core banking system at their association's base at the cost of three million dollars and the system has been in development for three years at the AEMFI's headquarters. The International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) covered more than half of the development cost while the institutions paid for the balance (Saverus, 2019).

IFAD's contribution is part of the second phase of a rural financial intermediation program that ended in 2019. It has provided a little over 100 million dollars in financing over the past decade. The Fund plans to extend 35.1 million dollars in grants and nearly five million dollars in loans to deliver rural financial services customized to fit the needs of smallholder farmers through the third phase, which kicked off last year. Close to 42 microfinance institutions serve five million customers, of which the majority reside in rural areas. They had mobilized 52.5 billion Birr in deposits by the end of last year and disbursed 69.3 billion Birr in loans (Saverus, 2019).

With the development of project management, certain methodologies became essential. These were gleaned from examining past triumphs and mishaps. For instance, the most effective strategies adopted by the government included implementing life cycle phases, utilizing templates such as work breakdown structure and risk management, and incorporating earned value measurement (Wideman, 2020)

Each organization must find their own best practice because no one approach can work for all. As people and businesses discover more efficient ways to achieve their goals, the process will continue to evolve. Some see standardizing templates and software across project management as their best practice. Many organizations have already implemented their own best practice without realizing it since it didn't originate from high-level decision-makers.

Although their methods may not be formalized within the organization, project managers often have their own approach to completing tasks that can be viewed as a highly effective practice. The process of carrying out a plan effectively is known as implementation. The success of a project plan implementation depends on achieving harmony between various critical elements, which can be categorized as structural and procedural. The structural elements refer to the organization's arrangement, highlighting the connections between its various components. On the other hand, the procedural elements include leadership, resources, and other administrative procedures. For a project plan to be executed correctly, it is essential to ensure compatibility between the company's structure and project plan. If there is any inconsistency, adjustments must be made to either the structure itself or the project plan.

(Mir & Pinnington, 2014) delves into the topic of accomplishing projects successfully by introducing the concept of "soft" and "hard" factors in implementation. The authors assert that for the project plan to be implemented there must be coordination between the soft elements, which include behavioral aspects, and the hard elements, which include analytical aspects of making and executing a project. The authors argue that

the crucial issue is finding a strategic fit between the soft and hard elements and organizational variables.

To achieve success, the support of all members of the organization is imperative, and thus, the top executives should be involved in the project from its inception. The authors emphasize the significance of leadership as the most influential aspect of the organization for the efficient implementation of a project.

Therefore, this study sought to evaluate management practice on implementation of core banking system in Member Microfinance institutions of AEMFI considering the factors in the available literature.

1.2. Background to Microfinance institutions under the AEMFI

Many NGOs have been providing low-interest loans to their beneficiaries since the 1970s, but default rates have been high. After consultations between government bodies and NGOs, a specialized institution was established to handle financial interventions in Ethiopia. The government issued its first microfinance legislation in 1996 to provide microfinance services to the poor through deposit-taking MFIs. The objective is to provide cost-effective and sustainable loans, micro savings, micro insurance, money transfers, and leasing to the large excluded population. The microfinance sector has shifted from humanitarian-oriented NGOs to specialized MFIs targeting financial sustainability and outreach. Other organizations are now prohibited from providing similar financial services to regulated MFIs (Morka & Wamatu, 2020).

The legal establishment of MFIs in Ethiopia was made possible by proclamation 40/1996. This has resulted in various MFIs being registered and able to offer microfinance services to both rural and urban areas, with the ability to provide deposit services and manage funds for microfinance businesses. While the Ethiopian microfinance sector is relatively new, it has seen rapid growth and has a focus on achieving scale and sustainability, particularly in serving rural households. Alongside

microcredit, a range of additional services such as micro savings, micro insurance, and micro pensions are now being provided. However, there is still a significant unmet demand for financial services in the country. MFIs have become a key source of microcredit, but other sources include commercial banks, SACCOs, government development programs, and informal sources such as money lenders and traders. According to AEMFI data as of March 2018, there are 34 registered MFIs in Ethiopia with a collective capital of nearly 12 billion Birr serving around 4.5 million clients (Morka & Wamatu, 2020)

The Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions was established as a non-for-profit, non-governmental association of the Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions which are formed as per Proclamation 40/1996 and regulated by the National Bank Ethiopian.

Currently AEMFI has more than 50 members MFIs providing microfinance services in the areas of credit delivery, saving, money transfer, and pension payment services in all regions of Ethiopia.

1.3. Statement of the Problem

Over the past few years, significant alterations in technology and communication have drastically transformed the financial sector. These innovations have enabled banks to provide round-the-clock customer service and to reduce wait times for customers. They have also enabled customers to access banking services from anywhere and at any time, increasing convenience and satisfaction. Additionally, these technologies have enabled banks to collect and analyze customer data, allowing them to personalize their services and tailor them to meet the specific needs of each customer. Overall, the adoption of information and communication technologies has been crucial for banks in enhancing their customer service delivery (Abebe, 2014).

Effective project management practices play a critical role in the successful implementation of any project. In Ethiopia, the core banking system is crucial for the

financial sector to provide efficient and reliable services to customers. The core banking solution deployed was acquired from Craft Silicon, a Kenya-based technology solutions provider. The project entails shared infrastructure (data center), core banking solutions, and technical support for all the institutions. Currently, the Ethiopian government has taken measures to introduce project management practices in the financial sector by establishing a Project Management Office, providing training and capacity building for project managers, and implementing project management methods and tools. In this regard Member Microfinance institutions have started the implementation task by establishing project team members, parameterizing the system, migrating the manual data to the system and providing end user training with different roll outings. Eighteen of the microfinance institutions in the project have already begun deploying the system, while some are finalizing the integration process. According to the, Executive Director of the AEMFI, the remaining member MFIs are lagging due to internal preparations (AEMFI, 2019).

Despite these initiatives, the implementation of the core banking system is still facing numerous challenges, including delays, high costs, and low customer satisfaction (NBE, 2022). Recent studies show that the adoption of the core banking system has not resulted in improvements in banking timeliness, cost-effectiveness, or customer satisfaction. For instance, the World Bank report highlights challenges in the integration of different banking platforms, inadequate infrastructure, and weak coordination among stakeholders (World Bank, 2019)

Despite of all the advantages core banking system brought to the member Microfinance institutions, Member Microfinance institutions of AEMFI has not done full implementation of core banking system and cannot get the targeted benefit from the system with delay and this has continued to escalate the operational costs. If the situation is not addressed the Member institutions are likely to face operational challenges and overall decline in their performance.

Therefore the study intended to evaluate the effect of project management practices on implementation of core banking system in Ethiopia with a case of selected Member

Microfinance Institutions of AEMFI and to the knowledge of the researcher, no research was done on project management practices on core banking system implementation in Ethiopia with a case of Member Microfinance institutions of AEMFI and there is a need to investigate the reasons for the limited adoption of the core banking system in Ethiopia despite the implementation of project management practices.

1.4. Objectives of the study

1.4.1. General Objective

The aim of the study was to assess how project management practices affect the implementation of shared core banking system in selected Member Microfinance Institutions of AEMFI, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.4.2. Specific Objectives

1. To assess the effect of stakeholder Management on implementation of core banking system project among member MFIs of AEMFI, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
2. To evaluate the effect of monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of core banking system project among member MFIs of AEMFI, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
3. To examine the effect of Risk Management on implementation of core banking system project among member MFIs of AEMFI, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.5. Hypothesis of the Study

Based on the research objectives and prior empirical investigations, the following hypotheses were established

H1: Stakeholder management has no statistically significant effect on implementation of Core banking system in AEMFI.

H2: Monitoring and evaluation have no statistically significant effect on implementation of Core banking system in AEMFI.

H3: Risk Management has no statistically significant effect on implementation of Core banking system in AEMFI.

1.6. Scope of the Study

1.6.1. Content scope

This study was intended to investigate the effect of Project Management Practices which was operationalized in terms of Stakeholder Management, Monitoring and Evaluation and Risk management on Implementation of Core Banking system which was operationalized in terms of banking timeliness, cost effectiveness and customer satisfaction.

1.6.2. Geographical scope

The study was conducted at Member Microfinance institutions of AEMFI located at Addis Ababa City Administration namely (Peace, Metemamen, Meklit, Eshet and Grand MFI).

1.6.3. Time scope

The study reviewed secondary data for the period 2017 to 2025 because this is the period when AEMFI started to adopt Br net core banking system that can digitalized member microfinance institutions and track their transaction with real time service delivery.

1.7. Significance of the Study

This study was bounded to be of benefit to the following stakeholders;

1.7.1. Project Managers

The findings will benefit project managers in the financial industry carefully assess the need for a new approach to project implementation. It will suggest the application of strategies that facilitate effective implementation of projects in the Member MFI institutions, with the aim of reducing unnecessary delays in the execution of sector-wide initiatives. Additionally, the findings will underscore the importance of

explicitly analyzing and evaluating project risk particularly in the context of their impact on the execution of projects by financial institutions in Ethiopia. This study will contribute significantly to the broader discourse on the subject.

1.7.2. Policy Makers

The findings will have a substantial impact on understanding the specific factors that contribute to the successful implementation of projects by financial institutions, and will also inspire greater acceptance of these factors in other types of projects and in the overall project implementation framework. Consequently, the results of the study can be leveraged to provide valuable project management recommendations for new, ongoing, and established endeavors, specifically for Core banking system projects carried out by financial sectors in Ethiopia. The findings will represent a solid foundation for policymakers to adopt established and effective models in their use of project management techniques.

1.7.3. The Public

The study can also indirectly benefit the public by contributing to improved efficiency, service delivery, and reliability of microfinance institutions. Enhanced project management practices can reduce operational delays and costs, ultimately leading to better financial services for customers.

1.7.4. Researchers and Academicians

This study will provide a comprehensive knowledge base for those in the academic and research fields interested in project management. It particularly focused on effective project implementation across different sectors, with a special emphasis on member MFIs of AEMFI. While the fundamental principles of project management are applicable to all fields, specialized focus is required for specific areas of application. In this case, the study centered on information technology projects in Member Microfinance Institutions of AEMFI.

1.8. Justification of the study

Numerous academic researches exist that detail the practice of project management in different project implementation. However, there is a lack of research on the assessment of project management practices in Microfinance institutions shared core banking system projects in Ethiopia. This research gap has spurred the current study, which aims to uncover how project management practices influence the implementation of Core banking system in the financial sector. By identifying flaws in project management practices, this study aimed to improve project delivery in selected Member microfinance institutions of AEMFI, and potentially others in the country. The Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institution can also benefit from the findings of this research, as it highlights areas for improvement in project management practices to get the intended benefit from the project within the financial sector. This study is the first of its kind in Ethiopia, and can serve as a foundation for future local and international research.

1.9. Definition of Terms

Stakeholder – institutional internal users those who can contribute more for the success the project implementation.

Implementation - refers to the actualization, performance, or application of a proposed strategy, approach, or framework for accomplishing a task, goal, or guideline.

Monitoring - regularly gathering and analyzing data to keep track of progress towards planned objectives and ensure that established guidelines are being followed.

Core banking system -is a software application or platform that enables banks and financial institutions to manage and process their key banking operations and customer data in a centralized, secure, and streamlined manner.

Project Management - utilization of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to effectively and efficiently carry out project activities in order to satisfy or surpass project requirements and expectations.

Risk Management - is an ongoing procedure of recognizing, examining, assessing, and dealing with potential losses and supervising safety measures and monetary assets to minimize the harmful repercussions of these losses.

Project Management Practices - refer to the set of techniques, protocols, systems, and guidelines utilized in the management of projects.

1.10. Conceptual Framework

This research focused on the accomplishment of a core banking system project as the dependent variable, with several factors as independent variables. These project management practice include stakeholder management, Project Monitoring and Evaluation and technological risk management.

The factors were selected after careful review of several articles and adapting the work of (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) and (Musau, 2015).

According to (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) the dependent variables were Timeliness, cost and quality and the study focus this factors as the main indicators of the implementation of Core banking system. Therefore, the variables are drafted from the above authors and by modifying by researcher's view.

Figure 1:-Conceptual Framework

Source: - Adopted from (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) and (Musau, 2015) and modified by Researcher, 2025.

The conceptual framework above has been developed to establish a clear correlation between variables in this research. This framework links the accomplishment of agreed-upon deadlines, expenses and quality in IT project implementation with certain actions, such as meeting deadlines, encouraging teamwork, achieving departmental goals and completing tasks, which ultimately contribute to increased efficiency, expertise, constructive feedback and effective organizational conduct. However, the study's independent variable is project management practices, which are displayed by risk management, stakeholder management, as well as project monitoring and evaluation.

Stakeholder management which can be expressed by Vendor involvement, user involvement and Communication is one of the independent variables of the study (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017). According to (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) the studies dependent variable of implementation of core banking system are measured by timeliness, Cost and quality.

The conceptual framework for this study is adapted from prior models (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017) and tailored to examine the implementation of core banking systems in Ethiopian microfinance institutions (MFIs). The choice of independent variables stakeholder management, project monitoring & evaluation, and risk management is based on both theoretical and practical considerations.

In Ethiopian MFIs, project success depends heavily on collaboration among internal staff and external parties due to limited resources and complex operational structures. Effective stakeholder management through vendor involvement, user engagement, and clear communication ensures alignment of expectations, reduces misunderstandings, and minimizes implementation delays (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017). MFIs in Ethiopia face challenges such as limited technical capacity and regulatory compliance requirements. Structured M&E practices allow organizations to track progress, detect deviations early, and implement corrective measures efficiently, improving the likelihood of achieving project objectives (Marrewijk, 2007)

Ethiopian MFIs operate in a context with high financial, technological, and operational risks. Identifying, assessing, and mitigating these risks is crucial to prevent delays, budget overruns, or system failures. Risk management ensures that projects are resilient to uncertainties inherent in developing-country contexts (Hillson, 2002)

The focus of this research is to emphasize how well-organized implementation and coordination of these project management factors can influence the timely completion of Core Banking system Projects.

1.11. Conclusion

In this chapter, the background of the study has been discussed. An explanation has been provided on both dependent and independent variables. The chapter emphasized the general research objectives to be addressed, Statement of the problem, Hypothesis of the study, scope of the study, Significance and justifications of the study as well as definitions of terms and conceptual framework of variables are discussed in detail.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter covers different works of literature on carrying out Core banking system projects. It begins by looking at well-known management theoretical reviews and their usefulness in executing projects effectively. The chapter returns to the basic conceptual framework, examining key elements such as involving stakeholders, managing risks, and monitoring and evaluating projects. These are all factors that affect the successful implementation of a core banking system. Additionally, the chapter examines empirical studies on this topic and highlight literature gaps with conclusion.

2.1 Theoretical Review

The research analyzed concepts from the fields of general and strategic management that are useful in project management. The study focused on exploring the applications of contingency theory and to enhance the effectiveness of Core banking system project management. The aim was to demonstrate how these concepts can be effectively integrated into project management practices.

2.1.1 Contingency Theory (Chris Argyris, 2013)

The theory of contingency suggested that projects differ from one another and therefore cannot be approached and handled in a uniform manner (Howell et al., 2010).

In the past twenty years, contingency theory has become increasingly relevant to project management, resulting in the development of dedicated frameworks influenced by research from a range of disciplines including innovation, organizational theory, management, computer science, product management, and engineering (Kureshi, 2013)

Contingency theory has led to a change in management principles by suggesting that a universal management strategy is not applicable for every project category(Howell et al., 2010).

The utilization of a specific or a combination of management approaches can prove advantageous to any undertaking undertaken by an organization. A lot of project management firms tend to choose a singular management technique and require adherence to its requirements for subsequent projects. Various project management methods exist and are employed by distinct project enterprises. Through contingency theory, companies can work together by reducing the importance of a uniform approach to project management (Howell et al., 2010).

The method of project management that takes into account unexpected events or circumstances, according to (Kureshi, 2013), It is necessary to evaluate how well project features align with the chosen method of project management. This aligns with research on long-standing organizational models that follow contingency theory, which suggests that the success of an organization depends on its ability to adjust to its surroundings and that there, needs to be consistency between the structure and the environment (Linton & Kask, 2017).

The contingency theory suggests that different environmental circumstances require specific organizational structures, and the effectiveness of an organization is determined by how well its structural elements align with external factors to accomplish share core banking project implementation.

Contingency theory proposes that there is no one best way to manage or lead an organization, and the most effective approach is dependent on the specific circumstances or contingencies of the situation. This theory is relevant to project management practice, as project managers often face complex and dynamic situations that require flexible and adaptive management approaches. Implementing a core banking system is a complex project that requires effective project management. The implementation process should take into account the unique organizational context,

including the requirements, culture, and resources of the organization. The contingency theory proposes that the project manager should adapt their management style and approach based on these organizational contingencies, such as the complexity of the project, the available resources, and the risk tolerance of the organization.

Thus, contingency theory provides a useful framework for project managers to tailor their management approach and implementation strategy to the specific needs of the organization during the implementation of a core banking system. The theory highlights the importance of adopting an adaptive and flexible approach to project management, which is critical in ensuring project success.

2.1.2 System Theory (Ludwig von Bertalanffy , 1940)

The systems theory is a way to arrange the way different components of a larger entity interact with each other. The main objective of the theory is to systematize data rather than clarify particular occurrences (Rousseau, 2015). A system refers to a structured entity composed of different elements that collaborate in a unique manner, separate from their interactions with other objects, and endures for a specific duration.

Based on the theory of systems provides us with the ability to comprehend the constituents and workings of client systems, thereby allowing us to analyze issues and create well-proportioned intervention plans that uphold the compatibility between individuals and their surroundings and understanding the fundamental structure of various complex systems is dependent on the interactions and relationships between their components. This knowledge can be applied to other systems with similar underlying issues (Tao & Tam, 2013).

Project managers, teams, funding agencies, consumers, time, budgets, and communication practices all share common fundamental factors. However, it is the interconnection and interplay between these factors that give each project its distinct character and dynamics.

(Farshchian et al., 2017) acknowledged that by those who have participated in projects that it can take a significant amount of time to observe the effects, and that minor factors may have a major impact on both the project and the people involved. Factors such as employee motivation and customer satisfaction are critical elements in this process, known as "human issues." Poor communication can cause disputes and the project to collapse slowly. Despite placing emphasis on addressing technical problems within projects, it is typically the result of human and informational difficulties that cause project failures.

(Ninan et al., 2019) States that Project managers have to handle intricate systems that involve many stakeholders, nonlinear elements, interdependent factors, and feedback loops. Common nonlinearities include unexpected alterations to the project's scope, the removal of crucial members, or the end of funding arrangements. Interdependencies refer to the links among the project team, stakeholders, clients, contractors, and suppliers. The rework cycles, progress updates, and performance reviews are all examples of feedback systems (Ninan et al., 2019).

The application of the systems theory will direct the exploration of the connection amongst distinct project management strategies and their effect on the implementation of core banking system project.

2.1.3 The Triple Constraint Theory (Van Wyngaard and Pretorius 2012)

(Van Wyngaard et al., 2012) proposed the Triple Constraint Theory as the framework for this research. According to them, this theory is crucial to project management and stems from the primary objective of the project, providing direction on how to limit the scope of the project. The concept forms a crucial element of the project blueprint and is indispensable for the consolidation and regulation of the project team.

Although there are various ways to explain the triple limitation concept, (Van Wyngaard et al., 2012) express a generally accepted understanding that project scope, time and cost are the three main factors of triple limitation. Project time refers to the planning and duration of the project, cost involves the budget and resources of the

project, and scope relates to the requirements and work of the project. (Mokoena et al., 2014) point out that a project with a limited time constraint is restricted by the completion motivation, while a project with a limited budget is restrained by the allocation of expenses. Projects with a limited scope are restricted by the performance standards of the expectations. Project quality is an essential component of project management and is supported by the triple limitation. The project management triangle is a useful model for illustrating the impact of changes on the triple limitation to important project stakeholders.

According to (Mokoena et al., 2014), the triangle reflects the interconnectedness of the three requirements and the fact that making changes to one side of the triangle can impact the others. The quality of tasks improves when all three factors of the triple constraint are balanced. It could be argued that projects that adhere to the triple constraint are among the most critical decisions related to actions.

The study is guided by this theory which explains how project performance can be measured by evaluating certain indicators such as scope, time, cost, and quality. In addition, project managers are responsible for managing risks that may arise during the project life cycle while adhering to the deliverables specified in the triple constraint theory.

The study is underpinned by Contingency Theory, Systems Theory, and the Triple Constraint Theory. Contingency Theory emphasizes that projects differ and require adaptive management approaches based on specific circumstances, guiding the study in examining how project managers tailor stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management practices to the unique context of each MFI. Systems Theory provides a framework for understanding the interrelationships and interdependencies among project components, such as project teams, stakeholders, resources, and communication processes, highlighting how these interactions influence the implementation of the core banking system. Triple Constraint Theory frames project performance evaluation by linking scope, time, cost, and quality, emphasizing the importance of balancing these factors to achieve successful project

outcomes. Collectively, these theories inform the conceptual framework of the study and provide a foundation for analyzing the effect of project management practices on core banking system implementation in member MFIs of AEMFI.

2.2 Conceptual Overview of project management practices

The idea of managing projects is clearly defined and comprehensible. (Too & Weaver, 2014) stated that although we know the reasons why projects fail and how to prevent it, they still do fail. According to the authors, failure in executing a project can be attributed to poor governance by the organization. Achieving good governance requires finding a suitable balance between restricting processes to prevent wrongdoing and giving management the flexibility to steer the organization towards productive growth and innovation, ultimately leading to the fulfillment of the organization's strategic objectives.

Project Management Practices are crucial elements that must be focused on to improve the performance of a project or program and effectively achieve a successful outcome. They represent the key aspects that require special attention (Golini et al., 2015). To ensure a project is successful, it is essential to establish a strong link between the project and the primary objectives of the institution. The project should align with the goals of the supporting organization and demonstrate how each task contributes to achieving those objectives. By doing so, the project will add the most value and provide the desired results. If this connection is not established, the project may meet its timelines, budget, and quality expectations, but fail to deliver the expected services or products (Izmailov et al., 2016).

With the evolution of project management, the significance of certain practices was recognized. Valuable insights were obtained from both successful and unsuccessful endeavors, resulting in the development of best practices. Such practices that were derived from government projects include the implementation of life cycle phases, use of templates such as work breakdown structure and risk management, as well as incorporating earned value measurement (Harold Kerzner, PhD, 2018).

There is no one-size-fits-all approach to best practices, as different organizations and situations call for different methods. As people and organizations come up with new and improved ways of achieving their goals, practices may evolve. Some organizations consider standardized templates and software as their best practices, while others may already have effective practices in place that were not officially endorsed by upper management. Although the methods used by project managers may not align with the formal processes of the organization, they tend to have their own preferred approach, which can be viewed as an effective method and classified as a best practice (Harold Kerzner, PhD, 2018)

This research examined three aspects of project management practices which were Stakeholder Management, Monitoring and Evaluation, and Risk Management.

2.2.1 Stakeholder management

According to authors, the incorporation of stakeholder management enhances the outcomes of core banking system project implementation (Di Maddaloni & Davis, 2017).

Stakeholders refer to persons or groups that have an impact on, or are impacted by, the results of a project (Aaltonen & Kujala, 2016). Certain research works concentrated on the identification of stakeholders and methods to allocate project-related focus equally among them (Aaltonen & Kujala, 2016) whereas While some explored how stakeholders' engagement can be made easier by comprehending their expectations (Chow & Leiringer, 2020).

The installation of core banking software can lead to a significant overhaul of the organization. This can result in potential risk if those involved in the project have a vested interest in the outcome, as they may exert pressure to meet their own requirements, increasing the complexity of the project. Therefore, achieving the maximum benefit from the core banking system requires the agreement and dedicated commitment of all internal stakeholders (Haralayya, 2021)

The prescriptive method for managing stakeholders in implementation of core banking system project involves identifying them and evaluating different factors to determine their concerns (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019). Engagement strategies are determined by evaluating the interests of the parties involved (Yang & Shen, 2015). Classically, the salience model defines the connection between an organization and its stakeholders are based on the level of influence each party possesses, the validity of their connection, and how pressing their demands (Mitchell et al., 1997). Another viewpoint evaluates how much stakeholders can affect core banking system implementation outcomes by considering factors such as their expertise, interpersonal abilities, monetary capital, and capacity for exerting influence outside of the organization (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019). The relational approach to stakeholder management argues that communication and relationships play a significant role in achieving shared goals and strategies for their strategies in a complementary manner (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019). According to the authors, trust relationships are benefited by effective communication (Chow & Leiringer, 2020). Additionally, it is important to take into account the views of stakeholders regarding Core banking system project goals and needs starting from the initial phases (Brunet & Forgues, 2019).

Understanding and satisfying stakeholders' needs are important for effective stakeholder management, and both methods are applicable in achieving this goal (Yang & Shen, 2015) and enhancing the outcome of the core banking system project (Di Maddaloni & Davis, 2017), which could be quantified by assessing the time and costs of the project. The Project Management office research also talks about stakeholders and how these offices help to enable and enhance their interactions and relationships with one another (Sergeeva & Ali, 2020) affecting the outcomes of projects in terms of cost and time.

Although studies on stakeholder management have demonstrated its positive impact on project outcomes (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019), no research has determined the effect of this influence, such as on the time and cost of core banking

system project under microfinance sectors. In the same manner, writers such as (Sergeeva & Ali, 2020) argue that project management office aids in managing stakeholders, however, there is no evidence to demonstrate the impact of stakeholder management and Core banking system project implementation outcomes. Consequently, two research inquiries are devised to fill these knowledge gaps.

Stakeholder management in Ethiopian Member microfinance of AEMFI has the practice of identifying and engaging with the various groups or individuals who have a stake in the microfinance institution's success, such as clients, investors, regulators, donors, and employees. The goal of stakeholder management in member MFIs of AEMFI is to build and maintain positive relationships with these stakeholders, which can help the institution to achieve its goals and objectives and mainly to develop shared infrastructure among them.

Member Microfinance institutions communicate with their stakeholders through newsletters, social media, or in-person meetings to provide updates about their activities and progress of Core Banking system implementation and strive to be transparent about their activities, financial performance, and governance practices. This can help to build trust with stakeholders and demonstrate the institution's commitment to accountability. Microfinance institutions collaborate with other organizations or stakeholders to achieve common goals.

By engaging with their stakeholders and building positive relationships, member microfinance institutions can better meet the needs of their clients and achieve their mission of implementing the shared core banking system at their Head of association in Ethiopia.

2.2.2 Project Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation during implementation of shared core banking system leads to projects success. The importance of monitoring and evaluating within financial institutions has become more significant because of the increasing influence of society. This has raised concerns about good delivery of products and the need for

more effective and efficient service (Nyaga Karani, 2014). Projects and institutional plans include evaluation statements; however, these statements are not applied in program activities or operations. Additionally, evaluation is not recognized as a valuable and extensive tool in areas of human activities. Evaluation is not standardized in the private sector and even less in the public sector (Nyaga Karani, 2014)

Monitoring and Evaluation share a common goal of assessing the efficiency, effectiveness, and impact of a project. Efficiency evaluates whether the input matches the output, while effectiveness measures how well a development program or project is meeting its objectives. Impact, on the other hand, gauges the difference made in addressing the problem at hand (Nyaga Karani, 2014).

Thus, monitoring and evaluation is the fundamental tool to run projects like different member institutions are shared for their service and it is a tool that's should be incorporated at all sectors of the nation to address the problems faced and to accomplish projects based on the scheduled period.

Project monitoring and evaluation in Ethiopian member MFIs of AEMFI have the experience of ongoing monitoring of Core banking system project and there is regular monthly meeting to evaluate the progress of the implementation of shared core banking system projects, outcomes, and to ensure that project goals are being achieved and to identify necessary modifications to improve project implementation and performance. This includes regular reporting, data collection and analysis, and stakeholder engagement to inform decision-making and adaptive management. Moreover, project evaluations are conducted periodically at AEMFI to assess the overall progress of the project.

2.2.3 Project Risk Management

The word risk has been present in the English language since the 17th century, and its origins can be traced back to its original meaning of encountering danger or coming into contact with a rock (Zou et al., 2017). The act of recognizing the primary hazards

in project management involves executing plans to detect and control significant threats that could impact a project, while defining the attributes of these types of risks. This process is fundamental in managing project risks.

In present times, the idea of risk is employed in various fields and expressed through diverse terms like danger or ambiguity and Risk management is a set of procedures designed to identify, measure and control any potential risks associated with a business venture or project (Zou et al., 2017)

According to (Ward & Chapman, 2003) due to the absence of a suitable measuring system for assessing and controlling project risks, the project incurred higher expenses and took longer time to complete. The author defines project risk as the likelihood of an event occurring that may not have a significant impact on the project objectives, but its possibility and effect are evaluated. Risk management involves a series of actions aimed at preventing potential risks from becoming a hindrance to a successful operation or leading to expensive rework. These actions include identifying, addressing, and eliminating risk factors (Jordan et al., 2013).

(Pramanik et al., 2020) noted that inadequately addressing and controlling potential risks could lead to various negative outcomes, such as higher expenses, alterations in financial structure, delayed in project implementation or office activities, disruption in financial planning, diminished revenue, potential legal claims, subpar final products, and changes to the project after completion.

The project's effectiveness, performance, excellence, and expenses are impacted by the presence of risk. The author recognizes risk management as a vital tool to handle unforeseen risks and surmount potential project difficulties (Akinbile et al., 2018).

Therefore, the success of the project will depend on completing it on time, staying within the allocated budget, and achieving key performance metrics, which are all contingent on the risk management skills of each team involved.

Member Microfinance institutions in Ethiopia are implementing various strategies to manage the risk associated with their projects specifically shared core banking system implementation. They have the strategy to assign focal persons at each Microfinance institution who has the responsibility to Identify the risk, analysis and controlling the risk related with core banking system project implementation. Overall, microfinance institutions in Ethiopia are continuously developing their risk management strategies to ensure the success of their projects and the sustainability of their operations.

2.3 Overview of implementation of core banking system

The methods used to carry out projects differ between companies and can even vary for different projects within the same company. It is widely acknowledged in current literature that there has been a significant increase in the importance and execution of projects and procedures in the business world over the last twenty years (Authors, 2015).

Project implementation refers to the finalization of plans and actions designed to meet the objectives of a project (Wang et al., 2017). During this phase, the project expectations are turned into tangible products and delivered to the customer. If the implemented project fails to meet the predefined parameters, it is considered a system failure. It is important to take into account that implementation requires more energy than anticipated and external limitations may arise, which need to be considered during the initial stage of the implementation process.

The most important project implementation is a highly competent project team and effective monitoring of project progress and project managers. Usually, the administration must take control of the main partner and the head of the company, which is often used or linked by the main partner. Company management must have an experienced and reliable administrative framework adapting to current needs and changing circumstances, because companies are rarely updated exactly as stated in the main contract. So far, the association should aim to provide high quality results and returns (Aaltola, 1997).

(Kyeremeh et al., 2019) states that the successful implementation of projects in Ghana mainly in information technology has resulted in the emergence of fresh markets, products and services and has improved the banking sector's delivery methods. Some instances include web-based digital banking, phone banking, and online banking. (Asad & Pinnington, 2013) stated that the implementation of information technology efforts played a key role in enhancing the competitive edge of commercial institutions by ensuring effectiveness and customer contentment. Recent changes in the financial sector have prioritized information technology for faster and more dependable financial transactions, as well as measures to enhance the industry as a whole.

Numerous investigations have been conducted regarding project implementation, and the results have been diverse. As an illustration, (Moradeyo, 2013) argued that if a project lacks efficient implementation, it is bound to fail since the original objectives and aims will inevitably change, which could call for a new implementation stage (Asad & Pinnington, 2013). Additionally, (Moradeyo, 2013) and (Issn, 2013) stressed the importance of information technology in the banking industry, emphasizing that it has had a remarkable impact on the growth and advancement of the sector.

This study focuses on cost effectiveness, timeliness, and customer satisfaction as indicators of the implementation of core banking system. These indicators are important in measuring the success of the implementation process, as they determine the overall effectiveness of the system. Cost effectiveness refers to the ability of the system to save costs and improve efficiency, while timeliness refers to the speed and accuracy of transactions. Customer satisfaction, on the other hand, reflects the degree of customer acceptance and utilization of the system. By examining these key aspects, the study aims to provide insights into the project management practice that influence the successful implementation of a core banking system project.

2.3.1 Cost effectiveness

Cost effectiveness pertains to how much an institution attains its desired goals by making the most out of its resources and lessening expenses. This encompasses

meeting the expected degree of output and excellence while keeping up with financial stability and effectiveness (Chit et al., 2015). Organizations are heavily impacted by cost effectiveness as it has a direct correlation with their profitability, financial stability, and ability to invest in growth and innovation. Effective management of costs and resources enables organizations to improve their financial position, boost competitiveness, and allocate resources towards the areas that generate value and underpin long-term success (Chit et al., 2015)

Basically, the efficiency of a project's expenses depends on the total worth of the resources utilized to produce more health benefits and in order for a policy maker to perform the calculation, they must have an understanding of the project's expenses, the amount of patients that will benefit from it, and the cost-effectiveness of the innovation or recommendation that will be carried out (Thompson et al., 2016).

Core banking solutions offer cost-efficiency benefits too. These systems are created to automate numerous tasks that were once performed manually, resulting in financial institutions being able to save money on labor expenses. Moreover, such solutions can be tailored to adapt to the specific requirements of each financial institution, which in turn decreases expenses even further. It is crucial for financial institutions to have cost-effective options because it allows them to provide more services to their clients without having to increase their operational expenses (Sultan, 2023).

Cost-effectiveness is a crucial measure of the implementation of the core banking system. Cost-effectiveness is achieved when the benefits accrued from the implementation are greater or equal to the investment made. The cost-effectiveness ratio is calculated as the total cost incurred divided by the benefits realized, which include increased efficiency, customer satisfaction, and profitability. A lower cost-effectiveness ratio indicates high cost-effectiveness, while a higher ratio indicates low cost-effectiveness.

Based on past occurrences, it has been observed that the implementation of core banking systems often results in a large number of failures. Roughly a quarter of these

implementations fail outright, with no progress made, while half don't meet their intended goals despite doubling their cost and implementation time. The causes for these failures may include inadequate information gathering during the planning phase, MFIs with unclear objectives, and scope changes during the project's development (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016).

Core banking services are now expected to have cost-saving measures in place. Many banks view core banking as a way to cut costs, since studies have shown that the cost per transaction using core banking is significantly lower than with other methods of service delivery, according to literature on ecommerce (Lemma, 2016).

The literature indicates that cost-effectiveness is a major consideration when implementing core banking systems. According to (Chauhan .2017), banks measure cost-effectiveness by evaluating the return on investment (ROI) from implementing the system. ROI is calculated as the net benefits derived from the implementation divided by the investment made. Banks that achieve high ROI from core banking implementation are deemed more cost-effective.

Similarly, (Yu, 2018) argues that banks use cost-benefit analysis to measure cost-effectiveness. Cost-benefit analysis involves evaluating the expected costs and benefits of implementing the core banking system. Banks that accomplish high benefits relative to the costs incurred are regarded as more cost-effective.

Therefore, cost-effectiveness is an essential measure of the implementation of the core banking system. It involves evaluating the benefits derived from the system relative to the costs incurred. Banks that achieve high cost-effectiveness exhibit a higher ROI and cost-benefit.

2.3.2 Timeliness

Projects involving the implementation of core banking software tend to take a larger amount of time and are more prone to extensions. Consequently, such projects are vulnerable to costs that escalate over time. As a result, banks that are striving to

modernize their core banking system must have a robust project management framework that keeps a close eye on the project's progress and mitigates possible risks (Haralayya, 2021).

The primary advantage of core banking solutions is that they enable customers to access their account details in real-time, enabling them to review account balances, track transaction history, and complete other banking activities without restriction. Such functionalities prove to be extremely useful for customers who are always on the move, as well as for those who prefer to conduct banking via the internet or mobile devices (Sultan, 2023).

One of the primary measures of successful implementation of a core banking system is timeliness. The ability of the system to deliver timely and accurate information is critical for the smooth functioning of the banking operations and helps to provide efficient services to the customers. Timeliness is an important parameter as it affects the bank's operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and profitability. Microfinance institutions should ensure timely delivery of services, which involves quick transaction processing and real-time data updates. The need of the hour is for Microfinance institutions to adopt an agile and flexible approach towards the implementation and maintenance of their core banking system projects. This will enable them to respond quickly to market changes and stay ahead of their competitors in an ever-evolving industry (Hsiao et al., 2017)

Timeliness also plays a crucial role in ensuring that the core banking system meets the regulatory requirements and compliance rules. Regulatory bodies require Microfinance institutions to maintain accurate and timely data across all operations, including customer transactions, deposits, withdrawals, and loan servicing. Failure to meet regulatory requirements can result in hefty penalties, fines, and loss of reputation, which can ultimately lead to the failure of the Microfinance institution (NBE, 2022).

In addition to regulatory compliance, timeliness also impacts customer experience. Customers expect quick and seamless banking services from their Microfinance institutions, including easy access to funds, easy application processes, and quick resolutions to their queries and transactions. Any delay or inconvenience can lead to customer dissatisfaction, which can impact the bank's reputation and customer retention.

In conclusion, timely and accurate delivery of core banking services is crucial for the success of Microfinance institutions. Microfinance institutions need to ensure that their core banking system is agile, flexible, and capable of meeting regulatory compliance requirements while providing efficient and seamless services to their customers. This requires a strategic approach towards the implementation and maintenance of the core banking system, aligning it with the MFI's business goals and objectives.

2.3.3 Customer satisfaction

The end objective of project implementation is to generate worth for both the company and the community. As per the success principle, company assets are utilized for the purpose of generating value through project results, pleasing stakeholders, building trust, advancing knowledge, achieving organizational credibility and so on (Derakhshan et al., 2019).

Core banking solutions have the crucial capability of managing various banking activities that comprise everything from credits and debits, applying for loans, transferring funds between accounts, and other similar tasks. As a result, financial institutions can provide a diverse array of customer services without necessitating the purchase of distinct systems for each kind of banking operation (Sultan, 2023).

Project should begin with the determination of customer requirements and it is essential to set project goals based on reducing the gap between the institutions expectation and actual performance especially in terms of delivery, timeliness and customer satisfaction (Coronado & Antony, 2002)

Customer satisfaction is a critical measure of the successful implementation of a core banking system. A core banking system is the backbone of a MFI's operations, and its successful implementation is crucial to delivering a seamless customer experience. When banks implement a new core banking system, they need to ensure that it aligns with their customer-centric strategy, enhances the customer experience, and meets customer expectations in terms of speed, convenience, and security (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016)

To evaluate the effectiveness of new core banking system, MFI's typically measure customer satisfaction through surveys, feedback forms, and credit scores. These metrics provide MFIs with insights into how their customers perceive the new system and whether it is meeting their needs and expectations. High customer satisfaction scores indicate that the core banking system is delivering the expected benefits and driving customer loyalty and engagement.

One of the main benefits of a core banking system is that it enables MFIs to offer more personalized services to their customers. This is achieved through a single customer view, whereby all customer information is stored in one place, making it easier for bank staff to access and utilize. This results in faster query resolution, improved response times, and more efficient transaction processing, all of which contribute to a better customer experience. MFIs can also offer more innovative products and services, such as mobile banking, online banking, and self-service options, which enable customers to manage their accounts and transactions with greater ease and flexibility (Ababa, 2022).

In Ethiopia, Financial institutions are struggling to provide efficient and pleasing services to their customers due to their reliance on conventional methods to offer banking services. Consequently, these banks are experiencing a situation where they have lost interest in the routine service delivery functions and the roles of their employees (Abebe, 2014).

Another benefit of a core banking system is that it enhances security and reduces the risk of fraud. With real-time monitoring and transaction checks, MFIs can spot suspicious activity faster and prevent fraudulent transactions from taking place. This helps to build trust and confidence among customers, who are increasingly concerned about the security of their financial data.

In conclusion, customer satisfaction is a vital measure of the successful implementation of a core banking system. By offering more personalized services, faster response times, and greater security, MFIs can increase customer loyalty and engagement, driving business growth and profitability. Through regular customer feedback and ongoing refinement of their systems and processes, MFIs can ensure that they continue to meet their customers' needs and expectations, delivering a seamless and frictionless experience (Abebe, 2014).

2.4 Empirical review

In this section several empirical studies that have been conducted in the areas of project management practices and their impact on project implementation are reviewed. The review follows the specific objectives of this study. This section provides a comprehensive overview of the relevant literature and helps to establish a solid theoretical foundation for the study.

2.4.1 Stakeholder management and Implementation of Core Banking System

There is evidence that indicates a strong and positive correlation between user engagement and the success of information technology projects (Sheffield & Lemétayer, 2013).

In their study (Alarafati et al., 2019), investigated how user engagement affects change management in the progress of developing information technology projects. A large corporation was analyzed in a case study, and the research categorized significant factors that contribute to successful project implementation. The importance of providing user training and up skilling opportunities was emphasized as

it enables stakeholders to enhance their skills and knowledge to effectively execute IT initiatives. (Bello-Pintado et al., 2019)state that projects in the realm of information technology are intricate systems and their successful implementation demands a comprehensive training program for both project teams and users.

Achieving optimum outcomes necessitates the establishment of a training infrastructure that enjoys the support and commitment of upper management. As per (Mazur & Pisarski, 2015)organizations that prioritize vital aspects of management like customers, stakeholders, workforce, and leadership perform better compared to those that don't. Furthermore, it is apparent that there exists a direct proportionality between the satisfaction levels of a team and their leader's performance, alongside a robust association between cooperative learning and the organizational environment.

According to (Olander, 2007) during the course of a project, there will be several individuals or organizations that have unique interests affected by it. The challenge is to recognize these project stakeholders and assess their needs and anticipations concerning the project goals to ensure that their requirements are fulfilled. Additionally, it is important to identify which stakeholders have the ability to influence project decisions.

According to (Achterkamp & Vos, 2008), Effective identification and management of stakeholders at the beginning of a project can benefit project managers as it leads to better project performance and increased profitability. According to (Achterkamp & Vos, 2008)the process begins with stakeholder categorization, followed by recognition of individuals involved, with the aim of aligning a role-specific framework to suit the project's surroundings. The strategy is influenced by stakeholders, and this influence is determined by the balance of power in the interaction between stakeholders and the firm.

This balance of power is affected by the level of the power base and the degree of interdependence between the parties (Frooman & Murrell, 2005). (Wood et al., 2021) examine the process of ranking stakeholder demands, which involves giving

preference to claims that are deemed urgent and credible, while also considering the stakeholder's ability to exert influence through effective use of power. According to (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019)Stakeholder management involves managing strategies for stakeholders that include these areas of focus.

2.4.2 Project Monitoring and Evaluation and Implementation of Core Banking System

According to (Kabeyi, 2019) project monitoring is the act of keeping an eye on a project or program is an ongoing process which is designed to offer management and interested parties with feedback on how well the project or program is progressing, or if there is any impediment to achieving the expected results whereas assessing progress towards desired outcomes or results that were planned systematically and objectively is the objective of evaluation, which is a selective exercise. This requires the evaluation of scope and depth, multiple times in response to changing needs to gain knowledge and learning. It is essential to note that evaluation must be continuous and not a one-time event or activity.

(Pollack, 2007) claimed that while monitoring and evaluation procedures serve as complements to each other and fall under the same project management function, they are perceived as separate processes and he argues that utilizing this method ensures a systematic and comprehensive monitoring process that can provide a complete and up-to-date account after the project's conclusion. Additionally, the flowchart implies a wider assortment of monitoring and evaluation methods and actions in the pre-project phase and a greater quantity of tools and activities during the project stage. Nevertheless, the number of evaluation techniques available at this level is less diverse because most actions follow a standardized procedure.

(Pollack, 2007) suggests that following a logical approach ensures a comprehensive and consistent monitoring process, allowing for real-time reporting of project completion. Most scholars recommended that more diverse monitoring and evaluation tools during the pre-project stage, and a higher amount of monitoring and evaluation activities throughout the project stage. Nonetheless, the scope of monitoring and evaluation techniques employed at this level is limited as most actions adhere to a standard approach.

(Moslemi Naeni et al., 2014) claim that after a project is completed, the amount and range of ways to monitor and evaluate it decrease, but the significance of the results is higher. When examining sustainable investment projects using the three categories of economic, social, and environmental aspects, while there are tools available to evaluate the impacts, there is no complete method for measuring the subjective social and environmental aims. (Sadiq et al., 2016) suggest that assessment can be a helpful tool for project planners and developers in determining whether their projects have met the objectives outlined in their project papers. Monitoring is crucial in avoiding schedule and expense overruns and ensuring that quality standards are met.

(Francis Macharia & Bowa, 2020) highlights that monitoring is aimed at improving day to day project operation while evaluation follows a research framework to assess how well the project objectives have been achieved. (Sulemana et al., 2018) emphasize the importance of establishing monitoring and evaluation systems from the early stages of a project, providing ongoing feedback mechanisms to make prompt management decisions.

2.4.3 Risk Management and Implementation of Core Banking System

Project risk management techniques involve the actions initiated by project managers to recognize and evaluate potential risks related to the project and effectively oversee these risks to reduce their impact on the project (Mutua & Caleb, 2020). The author explains that the process of managing risks involves a systematic approach of utilizing

the executive's plans, protocols, and tactics to identify, analyze, assess, mitigate, monitor, and communicate risks related to a particular situation.

As per PMI's guidelines for project risk management in 2013, essential risk management procedures must be carried out, which encompass planning, identification, analysis, response planning, and control of risks. (Maina & Ngugi, 2018) argues that project managers must consider the impact of risk on investment, as increased risk results in investors requesting greater returns, which ultimately affects the cost of projects, particularly those with limited duration.

(Selection, 2008) states that the integration of project risk management systems entails designing distinct frameworks and processes to manage and manage risks across all management levels. The effective deployment of risk management tactics hinges on merging risk management methods throughout all aspects of organizational management.

(Ellul & Yerramilli, 2013) emphasizes the importance of risk management in controlling risk exposure and preserving company assets and argue that the current context of heightened competition, rapid change, and uncertainty necessitates incorporating quality and risk as key factors in project management. (Bromiley et al., 2015) explains that risk management involves identifying variables that may prevent an organization from reaching its objectives and developing preventative strategies.

To initiate the process of identifying risks, the project documentation, current and past data are first assessed. Brainstorming can be employed to further facilitate the process, where the team works together to create ideas and solutions without any criticism or evaluation. Another technique, the Delphi method, can also be employed where a group of experts make predictions about possible risks to arrive at a consensus (Otieno, 2013). The author suggests that conducting interviews (in person, over the phone, via email, or through instant messaging) is another means of gathering risk information. Additionally, risk checklists may be used to identify risks by compiling a list of risks from past projects.

Risk analysis is a procedure aimed at evaluating and examining the dangers associated with a system. It can be performed periodically according to a set schedule, in response to an event, or when necessary. Additionally, it can be an ongoing process, where data and findings obtained from previous assessments are utilized in future risk analysis endeavors and the process of risk analysis involves examining the potential hazards and assessing their susceptibility and the consequences they may have. The likelihood and severity of the risks are also assessed. Risk management can be conducted both quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitative analysis involves using numerical data to determine the chance of negative events occurring and the potential magnitude of losses. On the other hand, qualitative risk analysis involves identifying potential threats, creating measures to address them, and evaluating the level of susceptibility (Otieno, 2013).

The methods for analyzing risk include Brainstorming, which is often utilized during the early stages of a project and can also be helpful in identifying and predicting potential risks for a specific project. This approach is straightforward yet practical, as it is intended to promote group creativity without fear or judgment from others. The objective is for each participant to expand upon previous suggestions without any negative feedback, with the purpose of fostering additional ideas that could inspire others (Otieno, 2013).

(Otieno, 2013) identifies sensitivity analysis as the second method of analyzing risks, which aims to evaluate the impact of altering a single variable in a project by analyzing its effect on the overall plan. This technique is considered the most straightforward way of conducting risk analysis, wherein uncertainty and risks are represented by specifying a possible range of variability for each element of the initial estimate. However, this kind of analysis is usually limited to variables that significantly influence the project's cost, duration, or financial returns, and those that have the most significant impact on the project's sensitivity.

Sensitivity analysis has several benefits such as demonstrating to management that there are various potential outcomes, making decision-making more practical but also

more intricate. In addition, it provides a clear picture of the significance of each variable that is being analyzed. However, this approach has certain drawbacks like treating each variable independently, thereby limiting the assessment of varied variable combinations. Furthermore, the sensitivity diagram does not provide any insight into the likelihood of an event happening in the future (Bhaumik, 2016)

Another technique for evaluating risk is probability analysis, which addresses the shortcomings of sensitivity analysis by assigning a probability distribution to each variable and examining scenario in which multiple variables may change simultaneously. However, determining the probability of each variable's occurrence can be challenging, especially because political and commercial circumstances can shift unpredictably. Like sensitivity analysis, the extent of variation is subject to individual interpretation, but when it comes to estimating project costs and timelines, the ranges assigned should be weighted towards potential overages, as project estimators are often overly optimistic or unintentionally neglectful in their estimations (Otieno, 2013).

Risk response and control refer to the measures taken in response to the risks that have been identified and those that remain, which includes executing risk response plans and assessing the efficiency of the strategies throughout the project's duration. This process also involves taking measures to improve opportunities and lessen the risks of achieving project objectives. Various precautionary strategies can be employed to put a certain method into effect.

The objectives of these risk control measures are intended to endorse the goals laid out in the risk management program, which in turn assist the aims of an individual or organization. Therefore, the risk control techniques used must be operational and practical, in accordance with legal requirements, promote the well-being of individuals, and guarantee business continues to operate in the aftermath of a loss (Otieno, 2013).

To achieve success in projects, it is important to establish a thorough project schedule and have a clear understanding of the critical factors for success. This will enable project managers and stakeholders to make informed decisions and take effective action towards project completion. Additionally, to ensure successful project delivery, it is vital to consider soft factors such as the development of soft skills that focus on maximizing customer satisfaction (Mutua & Caleb, 2020)

The Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institution (2017) applied a number of essential components for a strong project risk management system, which include: the involvement of a vigilant board and senior management; the establishment of appropriate policies, procedures, and limitations; the implementation of reliable risk monitoring and management information systems (MIS); and the establishment of appropriate internal controls.

2.5 Moderate Variables

The utilization of core banking solutions aids financial institutions in meeting regulatory necessities. As the number of regulatory demands grows, it is essential that financial institutions employ systems that allow them to adhere to such requisites. Core banking solutions are designed with incorporated compliance and reporting features, enabling financial institutions to fulfill their regulatory obligations and reduce the likelihood of penalties and fines (NBE, 2022).

Accordingly, the National Bank of Ethiopia has launched IT Management Framework directive for all MFI's to implement the core banking system which can also make positive influence on the implementation of the project indirectly.

2.6 Literature Gap

Based on a study of recent literature, microfinance institutions initiatives usually experience huge financial burdens, extended timelines, and issues with quality when they are completed. Delay refers to any extra time taken after the specified completion or delivery date for the project as agreed upon in the contract. These delays can have a negative effect on all parties involved and lead to losses, disputes, excessive expenses, legal actions, or even project abandonment. Certain studies have been conducted to identify the reasons for delay and develop methods to prevent them.

Despite the presence of literature on project management practices and success factors in this field, no research has been conducted on the effect of project management practices and the execution of core banking system projects under the microfinance sector. Understanding this connection could lead to improved project delivery.

Furthermore, although research exists on project management practices and their contribution to project success, there is a lack of studies investigating the effect of project management practices specifically stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management on the implementation of shared core banking system projects in MFIs. There is also limited understanding of how these practices influence project outcomes in the Ethiopian context, particularly among member institutions of AEMFI. This gap highlights the need for research that links specific project management practices to the successful implementation of core banking systems in MFIs.

Although there is existing research on project management techniques and various factors that contribute to project success, no study has been found that explores how the application of project management practices affects the execution of core banking system projects in Microfinance institutions. Understanding this correlation could result in the achievement of more triumphs in project (Hunde, 2021).

2.7 Conclusion

The literature review demonstrates that project management practices are critical to the success of projects; however, their application in the implementation of core banking systems within microfinance institutions is underexplored. By investigating this relationship, the present study aims to provide insights into how effective stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management can enhance project outcomes, reduce delays, and improve efficiency in Ethiopian MFIs.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

The term research methodology pertains to the structured sequence of steps used to carry out research work, including a range of techniques and protocols employed to gather, examine, and comprehend data (Mohammad Al Amaren et al., 2020). Ensuring that research is conducted in a stringent and scientific manner is a crucial element of any research endeavor.

Following the scholars mentioned above, this chapter is structured into 11 parts. These include an introduction, design of research, the population studied, determining sample size, techniques and procedures for selecting participants, methods for collecting data, instruments used to collect data, considerations for validity and reliability, procedures for collecting data, analysis of data, and obtaining ethical clearance. This organization is intended to ensure a comprehensive and scientific approach to the research.

3.1 Research Design

Research design refers to the overall plan or blueprint that guides the entire research process, from the formulation of research questions or hypotheses to the interpretation of results (Lindsay & Creswell, 2019). It outlines the strategies, techniques, and procedures used to collect and analyze data, directly impacting the validity and reliability of the study's findings.

This study employed a cross-sectional survey research design, which involves collecting data from a representative sample of participants at a single point in time using standardized questionnaires. The cross-sectional survey design was chosen because it allows for the examination of relationships among variables—specifically, stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management—and their effect on the implementation of the shared core banking system in selected member

microfinance institutions of AEMFI. This design is efficient, cost-effective, and appropriate for studies seeking to capture a snapshot of current practices and correlations between variables.

The study adopted a quantitative research approach, which involves collecting and analyzing numerical data to identify patterns, relationships, and trends (Quick & Hall, 2015). The quantitative approach was justified because it allows for the testing of hypotheses, measurement of the strength and direction of relationships among variables, and generalization of findings to the larger population. Using structured survey instruments ensures consistency, reduces researcher bias, and produces statistically reliable results. However, it is acknowledged that this approach may not capture intangible or subjective aspects of project management practices that are difficult to quantify.

Furthermore, a correlational analysis was employed to determine the strength and direction of relationships between independent variables (project management practices) and the dependent variable (implementation of the core banking system). While correlational design does not establish causation, it provides meaningful insights into how variations in stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, and risk management are associated with implementation outcomes.

In summary the combination of a cross-sectional survey design, quantitative approach, and correlational analysis provides a structured, systematic, and empirically robust framework for examining the effect of project management practices on core banking system implementation in Ethiopian MFIs.

3.2 Area of the study

The study was conducted at selected Member Microfinance institutions (Meklit, Peace, Metemamen, Eshet and Grand MFI) of AEMFI located at Addis Ababa city administration.

3.3 Study Population

When conducting research, it is important to consider the research goals, available resources, and feasibility of gathering data when determining the appropriate size of the study population. If the research is aimed at a particular group within the population, the study population should be limited to this subset of individuals.

There are around 25 Member Microfinance institutions in which some of them are implementing shared core banking system project and others are waiting to begin the implementation of core banking system project. From those MFI that has on the implementation phase the research selected five-member microfinance institutions (Meklit, Metemamen, Peace, Eshet and Grand) by considering their location and they are started the implementation process in different phases.

Thus, the group being studied in this research comprises of 120 individuals from selected member Microfinance institutions of AEMFI, as indicated in the table presented here below.

Table 1 Study Target Population

Member MFI	Unit of inquiry	Total Participants
Meklit MFI	1 Project Manager , 5 Project Member, 12 office administrators, 6 customer service officer	24
Metemamen MFI	1 Project Manager , 5 Project Member, 12 office administrators, 6 customer service officer	24
Peace MFI	1 Project Manager , 5 Project Member, 12 office administrators, 6 customer service officer	24
Eshet MFI	1 Project Manager , 5 Project Member, 12 office administrators, 6 customer service officer	24
Grand MFI	1 Project Manager , 5 Project Member, 12 office administrators, 6 customer service officer	24
Total		120

Source Primary Data (2024)

3.4 Research Procedure

The research procedure outlines the step-by-step process followed to collect, manage, and analyze data, ensuring that the study is systematic, reliable, and ethically conducted. The researcher reviewed relevant literature and defined the research objectives, research questions, and hypotheses. A detailed research plan was prepared, specifying the population, sampling technique, data collection methods, and analysis procedures.

Five member MFIs (Meklit, Metemamen, Peace, Eshet, and Grand) were purposively selected based on their stage of core banking system implementation and geographic locations. Target participants included project managers, project team members, office administrators and customer service officers directly involved in implementation. A structured questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale was developed to capture information on stakeholder management, monitoring and evaluation, risk management, and implementation outcomes. A pilot test was conducted with participants from one MFI to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability of the questionnaire. Necessary adjustments were made based on feedback.

Data were collected directly from participants through self-administered questionnaires. The researcher coordinated with MFI management to schedule data collection and ensured participants were informed of the study purpose, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Completed questionnaires were checked for completeness, coded, and entered into SPSS software for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize data. Correlation and regression analyses were conducted to test hypotheses and examine relationships between project management practices and core banking system implementation.

Findings were interpreted in relation to research objectives and theoretical framework. Recommendations were made based on the analysis, while maintaining ethical standards throughout the study.

3.4 Sampling procedure

Sampling involves selecting a portion of individuals or objects from a larger population to be a part of a research study. It is important to choose a sample that accurately reflects the characteristics of the population it was drawn from to ensure that the results of the study can be applied to the entire group.

In this study, both purposive and random sampling techniques were employed to ensure methodological rigor and relevance of data. Purposive sampling was used to identify and include key informants who possess specialized knowledge about the implementation of the Core Banking System. Their insights were considered essential for addressing the research objectives. At the same time, random sampling was applied to select general staff and other stakeholders from a larger population to minimize bias and ensure representativeness. By combining these approaches, the study benefited from both depth and breadth: purposive sampling ensures that critical expertise is captured, while random sampling provides a more balanced and generalizable perspective. This mixed approach strengthens the validity of the findings and enhances their applicability to the Ethiopian MFI context.

3.4.1 Sample Size

When designing research, it's crucial to take into account the size of the sample as it shapes the accuracy and precision of the results. It's necessary to make sure that the sample is big enough to have adequate statistical power and to reduce the chance of sampling error influencing the findings. But, an excessively large sample can pose a problem since it could result in unnecessary expenses and consumption of resources (Ishtiaq, 2019).

As a result, the study had a sample size of 92 participants from member MFIs of AEMF, selected using the Krejcie and Morgan table from (1970).

Table 2 Size of the sample and the methods used for sampling

Department	Target Population	Sample Size	Sampling technique
Project Manager	5	4	Purposive Sampling
Project Member	25	19	Purposive Sampling
Office Expert	60	46	Random Sampling
Customer Service Officer	30	23	Random Sampling
Total	120	92	

Source: - Primary Data (2024)

3.4.2 Sampling Technique

According to (Adwok J, 2015) a sampling technique refers to the method applied to choose a specific number of individuals from a population. The author further states that the effectiveness of representing a population depends on several factors including the suitability of the sample frame to the population description, the implementation of a sampling procedure that offers each person an equal opportunity for selection, and whether the technique can impact the accuracy of sample estimates.

The technique of **simple random sampling**, which is a type of probability sampling, was chosen due to the fact that each individual in the population had an equal opportunity to be chosen for the sample. Additionally, the population was considered homogenous and there was no previous knowledge regarding the population's characteristics (Sharma, 2017)

Purposive sampling is a type of sampling that doesn't rely on probability and is chosen because participants are selected based on specific traits or standards that are important to the research question. The researcher intentionally picks participants who can likely offer the relevant information or represent the group being studied (Sharma, 2017).

3.5 Sources of data

3.5.1 Primary source of data

The reason this data is favored is because it is obtained directly from the origin using means such as conducting studies, performing tests, making observations, and having discussions. As a result, it is frequently viewed as being more dependable and precise (Chaln Chavez & Guevara Paredes, 2014)

3.5.2 Secondary source of data

Another form of data, known as secondary data, can complement primary data through its valuable background information and context for research studies. It is data that has been previously collected and published by government agencies, research institutions, or other organizations (Mirzakhanyan, 2005)

3.6 Data collection methods

Structured surveys with closed-ended questions were developed to gather data from project managers, project members, office expert, and Customer Service officer involved in core banking implementations. Understanding the effectiveness of project management practices in the implementation of core banking systems and identifying challenges faced during the process. Define the population from which data will be collected, such as project managers, project members, office expert, and Customer Service officer involved in the core banking system implementation in selected member Microfinance institutions of AEMFIs. A simple random sampling was used to select participants. This ensures a representative sample of the population. Develop a questionnaire. Distribute the survey using paper surveys.

Ensure participants understand the purpose of the survey and how their data were being used. Survey provides a versatile way to gather data for research purposes. Data were collected from project managers, project members, office expert, and Customer Service officer involved in the core banking system implementation in selected member

Microfinance institutions of AEMFIs. The developed questionnaire was administered to the selected subjects in selected Microfinance institutions at their places of work through hand delivery. The researcher was requested to collect the daily filled questionnaire from the respondents work stations after they were filled.

3.7 Data collection instruments

The tools utilized to gather data comprised of the following

3.7.1 Questionnaire

Questionnaires are prevalently employed to collect data, leading many inexperienced business, management, and social science researchers to equate research with questionnaires.(Rowley, 2014).

To comply with this, the researcher was the one to distribute the questionnaires to all types of respondents at selected member microfinance institutions. The questionnaire comprised questions with limited choices to collect numerical data. A Likert scale that ranged from 1 to 5 was used, wherein the respondents indicated their agreement level from strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree, and the data collected measured how variables were interconnected.

3.8 Quality Control tests

3.8.1 Validity

Validity is the extent to which an experiment or measure accurately depicts or represents the idea or occurrence being examined and an accurate measure or experiment is one that evaluates the desired aspect precisely, without any interference from other factors (Gomm, 2008). According to (Heale & Twycross, 2015) Validity in a quantitative study is the degree to which a concept is accurately measured.

The assessment of the adequacy of this research is conducted by using the Content Validity Index (CVI), which evaluates the extent to which a collection of items or

queries accurately depict the subject matter or category being studied. (Taherdoost, 2018) explains that Content validity refers to the extent to which the items in an instrument accurately reflect the content that the instrument is intended to measure.

The process of determining the CVI involves experts assessing each item's relevance to the construct or domain, and the resulting ratio of items deemed relevant is considered the CVI.

Waltz, Strickland, and Lenz recommended in their 2005 book "Measurement in Nursing and Health Research" that a Content Validity Index (CVI) score of 0.7 or above is an indication of a valid tool. They advised that a CVI score of 0.7 or higher is an acceptable threshold for establishing content validity and

(Lynn M. R., 1986) suggests that an instrument with a score of 0.7 CVI or higher is considered valid.

The Content Validity Index (CVI) is given by the formula.

$$CVI = \frac{\text{no of questions Declard valid}}{\text{Total No. of items in the questionnaire}}$$

On my proposal I had a 35-item questionnaire distributed for 10 experts to assess the validity of items and after evaluation, 30 out of the 35 items are declared valid (Counted Relevant and most relevant) by among experts and using the above formula content validity index computed a simplified CVI as:

$$CVI = \frac{30}{35} = 0.86$$

This means that 86% of the items are considered valid and can be used for further research processing.

3.8.2 Reliability

Reliability refers to the degree to which the study can be replicated with identical outcomes. In the case of the survey, reliability is determined by the accuracy and completeness of the responses obtained and the ability to ensure that respondents fully comprehend the questionnaire (Heale & Twycross, 2015)

To ensure the reliability of the data, the researcher used the test-retest method to measure the research instruments before conducting the study. This involved checking if the variables and questions provided consistent answers. Both in the field and outside, the researcher double-checked to eliminate any errors or omissions.

The researcher also administered a sample questionnaire to respondents from five member MFs of AEMFI in Addis Ababa at various intervals to assess how the questions were answered. Any unclear or ambiguous questions were modified based on this feedback.

The study's reliability is confirmed by using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, a widely utilized method in research to evaluate the precision of scales and questionnaires. A high Cronbach's alpha coefficient indicates that the items in the measure are closely related and probably measuring the same concept (DeVellis, 2017).

A pilot study was carried out to assess the reliability of the questionnaires. Subsequently, an evaluation of consistency was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha, which examines whether different items within a scale measure the same concept. The acceptable alpha value, as stated by (Klien, 1999), is 0.7, which was used as the standard in this study. Cronbach's Alpha was computed for each scale vector as follows.

3.8.2.1 Stake Holder Management Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items

.820	.762	8
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The reliability analysis conducted on the SPSS tool yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.820 which is above 0.7, indicating high internal consistency among the 8 items. This suggests that the items in the tool reliably measure stake holder management for further use in research and assessment context.

3.8.2.2 Monitoring and Evaluation Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.879	.882	10

The reliability analysis conducted on the SPSS tool yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.879 which is above 0.7, indicating high internal consistency among the 10 items. This suggests that the items in the tool reliably measure Monitoring and Evaluation for further use in research and assessment context.

3.8.2.3. Risk Management Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.817	.756	8

The reliability analysis conducted on the SPSS tool yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.817 which is above 0.7, indicating high internal consistency among the 8 items. This suggests that the items in the tool reliably measure risk management for further use in research and assessment context.

3.8.2.4. Implementation of Core Banking System

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.830	.844	9

The reliability analysis conducted on the SPSS tool yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.830 which is above 0.7, indicating high internal consistency among the 9 items. This suggests that the items in the tool reliably measure Implementation of core banking system for further use in research and assessment context.

3.9 Data Analysis

Data analysis involves changing unprocessed data into useful information that can be utilized for decision-making, concluding, or gaining deeper knowledge and understanding (Field, 2005). Data analysis employs a range of approaches and procedures, such as descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

3.9.1 Quantitative data

The process of analyzing quantitative data will utilize statistical methods to interpret and make sense of numerical information (Ishtiaq, 2019). The methods incorporate both measures of central location, such as the mean, and measures of how spread out the data is, such as the standard deviation (Ishtiaq, 2019) and as a result of using inferential statistics like correlations and regressions, the researcher can draw valid conclusions and make suggestions backed by factual evidence (Field, 2005)

3.10 Measurement of Variables

The act of measuring variables is an essential factor in the process of conducting research, since it enables investigators to acquire information that can be scrutinized and elucidated in order to arrive at pertinent inferences (Heilmann, 2018)

Nominal scales were utilized for the measurement of categorical variables with unique categories or levels, such as demographic information of survey participants, wherein values were assigned to each category for identification (Field, 2005). Ordinal variables consist of categories that can be placed in a particular order; however, the distinction between the categories may not always be uniform. The measurement of

an ordinal variable such as a Likert scale involved the utilization of an ordinal scale (Heilmann, 2018).

3.11 Ethical considerations

The moral aspects of research are critical because they ensure that the research is carried out in a manner that honors ethical principles and standards, demonstrates responsibility, and is considerate of all parties involved (Appelbaum et al., 2018). Research ethics involve ensuring that informed consent is obtained, confidentiality is maintained, and the individuals participating in the research are safeguarded from any potential harm (Appelbaum et al., 2018)

Obtaining informed consent was crucial for ethical research, which means that participants were not be persuaded in any way and were have the choice to participate in the study voluntarily, with the freedom to withdraw anytime they choose. Upholding confidentiality was another significant ethical principle in research, therefore, the researcher were committed to ensuring participants' privacy and anonymity, and keeping any personal data confidential. Acknowledging and crediting any information sourced from other scholars was an important aspect of this work.

Furthermore, ethical clearance for this study was obtained from the Uganda Martyrs University. In addition, permission was secured from Selected MFIS management prior to data collection to ensure institutional compliance and cooperation.

The researcher acknowledged that their study was built on numerous ideas from different scholars and contributes towards the ongoing effort of generating knowledge that other researchers can also benefit from.

3.12 Limitations of the study

A number of participants were hesitant to provide the necessary information to the researcher due to defensive behavior, time constraints, and doubts. As a result, the researcher emphasized the significance of the study and collaborated with Institutional Chief Executive officer (CEO) to raise awareness. Issues such as inaccuracies and

intentional falsification of data also arose in the field. To mitigate this, the researcher ensured the research instruments precise before commencing the study and cross-checked the data by examining the relationships between various responses. Language barriers also make difficulties, with some respondents experiencing difficulty reading and understanding the questions. Consequently, the researcher used more informal English and local language to simplify the language and enhance communication.

3.13 Conclusion

In this chapter, the techniques used to gather pertinent information needed to accomplish the study's objectives were discussed. An explanation is provided on how the data is collected and processed to enable informed analysis of the findings. The chapter emphasized the general research plan to be employed, which details the approach taken in the research design, identification of the study population, determination of sample size and sampling procedures, selection of data collection approaches and tools, as well as data analysis and variable measurement.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the study's results. It outlines the response rate, the demographic details of the respondents, and the empirical findings, structured according to the study's objectives. These objectives center on Stakeholder Management, Monitoring and evaluation, change and Risk Management as independent variables, in relation to Implementation of Core banking system as the dependent variable.

4.2. Response rate

The researcher began with a total population of 120 and selected a sample size of 92 using the Krejcie and Morgan table. Out of those sampled, 76 respondents completed and returned their questionnaires, resulting in a response rate of 82.6%. According to scholars such as Mugenda & Mugenda (2005) and (Sitiza & Wood, 1998), a response rate of 50% or higher is considered sufficient when collecting quantitative data. Thus, the 82.6% response rate was viewed as favorable and indicates that the survey results are representative of the study population.

4.3. Bio data of respondents

4.3.1. Gender of respondents

This section examines the gender of respondents which was categorized as male and female. A question about gender of respondents was administered and the results were analyzed using descriptive statistics (Table 8)

Table 3: Gender of Respondents

Gender of respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	29	38.2	38.2	38.2
	Male	47	61.8	61.8	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data (2024)

The findings in table 8, above revealed that majority of the respondents were male (61.8%) followed by the female at 38.2%. This may imply Microfinance Institutions in Ethiopia have more male workers than female. However, there is relatively gender sensitivity.

4.3.2. Age of respondents

Table 4: Age of respondents in years

Age of respondent					
Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age of respondent	18-30	26	34.2	34.2	34.2
	31-40	30	39.5	39.5	73.7
	41-50	14	18.4	18.4	92.1
	>50	6	7.9	7.9	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data (2024)

The findings in table 9 above revealed that majority of the respondents were in the age group 31 - 50 years (39.5%), followed by 18-30 years (34.2%) whereas 41-50 years have 18.4% and lastly 7.9% for above 50 years. The findings imply that all the respondents were mature and experienced enough about the subject matter to give reliable responses.

4.3.3. Highest Level of education of respondents

Table 5: Level of education of respondents

Level of education of respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma	13	17.1	17.1	17.1
	Degree	46	60.5	60.5	77.6
	Masters and Above	17	22.4	22.4	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data (2024)

The study findings revealed that majority of the respondents were Degree holders (60.5%), followed by Master holders (22.4%), and lastly Diploma holders (17.1%). The findings also imply that most of the respondents were educated enough to understand the question under investigation and interpret the study tool (Table 10).

4.3.4. Working experience of respondents

Table 6: Work Experience of respondent

Work Experience of respondent					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5	15	19.7	19.7	19.7
	6-10	22	28.9	28.9	48.7
	11-15	25	32.9	32.9	81.6
	>15	14	18.4	18.4	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data (2024)

The findings revealed that majority of the respondents had worked from 11- 15 years (32.9%), followed by 6– 10 years (28.9%), 1 – 5 years (19. 7%) and lastly above 15

years (18.4). The findings imply that most of the respondents were experienced enough hence reliability of findings (Table 11).

4.3.5. Position of the Respondents

Table 7 Position of respondents in the project

Position of respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Project Manager	5	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Project Member	16	21.1	21.1	27.6
	Office Expert	37	48.7	48.7	76.3
	Customer Service officer	18	23.7	23.7	100.0
	Total	76	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data (2024)

The findings in table 12 above revealed that majority of the respondents were working in the position of office expert (48.7%), followed by Customer Service officer (23.7%) whereas project members have 21.1% and lastly 6.6% for Project Managers. The findings imply that most of the respondents have enough knowledge about the subject matter to give reliable responses.

4.4. Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive statistics was interpreted basing on the 5 point Likert scale [strongly disagree (1.0 - 1.9), disagree (2 - 2.9), Neutral (3.0 - 3.9), Agree (4.0- 4.5), strongly Agree (4.5 - 5.0).

The standard deviation (SD) indicates how much the individual data points typically deviate from the mean. A low standard deviation suggests that the data points tend to be close to the mean generally between 0 and 1 (or a small number relative to the mean). A moderate standard deviation indicates a reasonable spread of data points around the mean often between 1 and 2 (around 25% to 50% of the mean). While a

high standard deviation indicates that the data points are spread out over a wider range of generally greater than 2)

4.4.1. Descriptive Statistics on Stakeholder Management

The aim of the study was to assess how stakeholder management influences the implementation of the Core Banking System. Consequently, the participants were presented with statements to rate using a 5-point Likert scale. The results are summarized in table 14.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics for Stakeholder Management

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
At every step of the project, stakeholders play a role.	76	2	5	3.20	.731
Institution identifies and addresses the concern of stakeholder.	76	2	5	3.78	.759
Stakeholders are well-informed about the project and their expectations are met.	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
Assessing the needs and expectation of stakeholders in relation to project objectives is challenging	76	3	5	4.12	.952
Decisions regarding the project are influenced by the need and expectation of stakeholders	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
There was effective communication with stakeholders	76	4	5	4.51	.503

Regular feedback from stakeholders helps to measure the success of project implementation	76	4	5	4.51	.503
Building strong relationship with stakeholders leads to long term support and collaboration for future system enhancement	76	4	5	4.49	.503
Valid N (listwise)	76				

Source: *Primary data (2024)*

The mean (or average) is a measure of central tendency that summarizes the typical or average response in a dataset while the standard deviation quantifies the amount of variation or dispersion in a set of values.

Respondents were required to indicate if stakeholders play a role at each stage of the project; findings showed a mean value of 3.20, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are moderately involved in the project stages while the standard deviation of 0.731 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the role of stakeholders across the project stages (Ninan et al., 2019).

Respondents were required to indicate if institution identifies and addresses the concern of stakeholder; findings showed a mean value of 3.78, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are moderately involved in the project stages while the standard deviation of 0.759 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the concern of stakeholder across the project stages (Haralayya, 2021).

Respondents were required to indicate if Stakeholders are well-informed about the project and their expectations are met; findings showed a mean value of 4.03, which

implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the project stages while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points are likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036. This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding well-informed of stakeholder across the project stages (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016).

Respondents were required to indicate if assessing the needs and expectation of stakeholders; findings showed a mean value of 4.12, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the project stages while the standard deviation of 0.952 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the assessment, the needs and expectation of stakeholders across the project stages (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016).

Respondents were required to indicate if decisions regarding the project are influenced by the need and expectation of stakeholders; findings showed a mean value of 4.03, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the project stages while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points are likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the project are influenced by the need and expectation of stakeholders across the project stages (Wood et al., 2021).

Respondents were required to indicate if there was effective communication with stakeholders; findings showed a mean value of 4.51, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the project effective communication while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding effective communication with stakeholders (Chow & Leiringer, 2020).

Respondents were required to indicate if regular feedback from stakeholders helps to measure the success of project implementation; findings showed a mean value of 4.51, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the regular feedback while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding Regular feedback from stakeholders across the project implementation (Abebe, 2014).

Respondents were required to indicate if building strong relationship with stakeholders leads to long term support and collaboration for future system enhancement; findings showed a mean value of 4.49, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that stakeholders are highly involved in the building strong relationship with stakeholders. The standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding Building strong relationship with stakeholders leads to long term support and collaboration for future system enhancement (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019).

The results of this study align with the conclusions drawn by(Wood et al., 1997) who explain the prioritization of stakeholder claims. They argue that a claim is given higher priority when it is perceived as legitimate and necessitates immediate action, particularly if the stakeholder possesses the power to influence the outcome.

Furthermore, (Chow & Leiringer, 2020) notes that stakeholder management typically involves strategies that address these traditional areas of emphasis to meet their expectation.

4.4.2. Descriptive Statistics on Project Monitoring and evaluation

The research aimed to assess how significantly project monitoring and evaluation affect the implementation of the core banking system and the respondent's analysis are discussed in the following table 15.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics for Project Monitoring and Evaluation

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Monitoring over the project improves the excellence of its project management.	76	3	4	3.51	.503
The project's progress is receiving adequate feedback.	76	3	4	3.49	.503
Monitoring quality standards	76	2	5	3.70	.766
Assessment through evaluation can assist planners in determining the degree to which the objectives of the projects have been attained.	76	3	5	4.41	.677
Accurate information regarding the project is gathered and assessed.	76	2	5	4.26	1.226
Monitoring activity supports both project managers and staff in understanding whether the projects are progressing on schedule or meet their objectives	76	2	5	3.54	1.509
There is a regular and careful progress (time, scope, and cost) monitoring and review throughout the project	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
There exists contingency plans in running the project	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
Each stage undergoes a periodic assessment to evaluate project outcomes.	76	4	5	4.51	.503
There is a necessary report on the project performance	76	2	3	2.51	.503
Valid N (listwise)	76				

Source: Primary data (2024)

Respondents were required to indicate if monitoring over the project improves the excellence of its project management; findings showed a mean value of 3.51, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that Monitoring is moderately involved over the project improves the excellence of its project management while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the role of Monitoring across the improvement of the excellence of its project management (Nyaga Karani, 2014).

Respondents were required to indicate if the project's progress is receiving adequate feedback; findings showed a mean value of 3.49, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that project's progress is moderately involved over receiving adequate feedback while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the project's progress across receiving adequate feedback (Haralayya, 2021).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is monitoring quality standards; findings showed a mean value of 3.70, which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that monitoring quality standards is moderately involved over receiving adequate feedback while the standard deviation of 0.766 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the monitoring quality standards across project management (Francis Macharia & Bowa, 2020).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is accurate information; findings showed a mean value of 4.26 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that accurate information is highly involved over the project is gathered and assessed while the standard deviation of a standard deviation of 1.226 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.034 and 5.486. This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the project across

accurate information (Hsiao et al., 2017).Monitoring activity supports both project managers and staff in understanding whether the projects are progressing on schedule or meet their objectives

Respondents were required to indicate if monitoring activity supports both project managers and staff in understanding whether the projects are progressing on schedule or meet their objectives; findings showed a mean value of 3.54 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that monitoring activity supports both project managers and staff is moderately involved in understanding whether the projects are progressing on schedule or meet their objectives while a standard deviation of 1.509 with a mean value of 3.54 indicates most data points were likely to range between 2.031 and 5.049. This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the project Monitoring activity across project managers and staff (Pollack, 2007).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is a regular and careful progress; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that regular and careful progress is highly involved in time, scope, and cost while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding the regular and careful progress across time, scope, and cost (Abebe, 2014).

Respondents were required to indicate if there exists contingency plans in running the project; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there exists contingency plans is highly involved in running the project while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points are likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding exists contingency plans across the project (Linton & Kask, 2017).

Respondents were required to indicate if each stage undergoes a periodic assessment to evaluate project outcomes; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that each stage undergoes a periodic assessment to evaluate project outcomes is highly involved to evaluate project outcomes while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding each stage undergoes a periodic assessment across the project outcomes (Francisco de Oliveira & Rabechini, 2019).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is a necessary report on the project performance; findings showed a mean value of 2.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there is a necessary report on the project performance is low (slightly more positive) to evaluate project outcomes while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding each stage undergoes a periodic assessment across the project outcomes (Linton & Kask, 2017).

The study results concur with the findings of (Sulemana et al., 2018) who concluded that monitoring and evaluation were regarded as core tools for improving the implementation of core banking system taking into account that managing complex projects in the short and medium run will involve corresponding financial strategies, which were supposed to respect the criteria of effectiveness, sustainability and durability and this study aligns with existing literature on Project Monitoring and evaluation (Francis Macharia & Bowa, 2020)

4.4.3. Descriptive Statistics on Risk Management

The study also aimed to evaluate how project risk management impacts the execution of core banking system within the Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions as discussed in Table 16.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics for Risk Management

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Risk is considered key factors for a performance management	76	2	5	3.09	.677
Risk assessment at the beginning of the project is conducted	76	2	5	3.78	.759
Identified risks are analyzed	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
The project has enough data on events	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
There is proper communication on the risks	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
The management encourages the reporting of events in order to identify risk	76	4	5	4.51	.503
There are proper mechanisms to mitigate project risk	76	4	5	4.51	.503
There is a risk review process, after implementation of the Mitigation measures for identified risk.	76	4	5	4.49	.503
Valid N (listwise)	76				

Source: *Primary data (2024)*

Respondents were required to indicate if risk is considered key factors for a performance management ; findings showed a mean value of 3.09 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that risk is considered key factors for a performance management is moderately involved for a performance management while the standard deviation of 0.677 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding Risk across performance management (Bromiley et al., 2015).

Respondents were required to indicate if risk assessment at the beginning of the project is conducted; findings showed a mean value of 3.78 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that risk assessment at the beginning of the project conducted is moderately involved for a performance management while the standard deviation of 0.759 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the

responses, indicating that most respondents have similar perceptions regarding Risk assessment across the beginning of the project (Zou et al., 2017).

Respondents were required to indicate if identified risks are analyzed; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that identified risks are analyzed is highly involved for a performance management while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean in identified risks across the analysis of the project (Otieno, 2013).

Respondents were required to indicate if the project has enough data on events; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that the project has enough data on events is moderately involved for risk management while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean in enough data on events across the project (Linton & Kask, 2017).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is proper communication on the risks; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that proper communication is highly involved on the risks while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean in proper communication across the project (Linton & Kask, 2017).

Respondents were required to indicate if the management encourages the reporting of events in order to identify risk; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that management encourages is highly involved in order to identify risk while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that

there is a relatively low level of variability in management encouragement across the reporting of the project (Kureshi, 2013).

Respondents were required to indicate if there are proper mechanisms to mitigate project risk; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there were proper mechanisms risk is highly involved to mitigate project while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in proper mechanisms to mitigate project risk across the project (Zou et al., 2017).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is a risk review process; findings showed a mean value of 4.49 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there were proper mechanisms risk is highly involved to mitigate project while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in proper mechanisms to mitigate project risk across the project and this study aligns with existing literature on Risk Management (Ellul and Yerramilli, 2013, Maina and Ngugi, 2018)).

4.4.4. Descriptive Statistics on Core Banking System Implementation

Table 11 Descriptive Statistics for Core Banking System Implementation

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Maxi	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is improvement in the response time towards customers' queries since the implementation of core banking system.	76	3	4	3.51	.503
There is reduction in the time taken to process financial services, such as deposits, withdrawals, or loan disbursements, since the implementation of the Core Banking System.	76	3	4	3.49	.503
There is faster resolution of	76	2	5	3.80	.731

financial-related issues or concerns within your microfinance institution					
The institution has witnessed more automation of tasks to replace those manually done previously.	76	4	5	4.51	.503
The overall costs associated with financial services have decreased	76	2	5	4.26	1.226
There is a satisfactory return on investment being registered by your institution.	76	4	5	4.51	.503
There are more personalized services being offered to customers by the institution.	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
Complaints from customers regarding the services have gradually reduced.	76	3	5	4.03	1.006
There is positive feedback from customers in regard to security and response time from the institution	76	4	5	4.51	.503
Valid N (listwise)	76				

Source: *Primary data (2024)*

There is improvement in the response time towards customers' queries since the implementation of core banking system.

Respondents were required to indicate if there is improvement in the response time towards customers' queries; findings showed a mean value of 3.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there is improvement in the response time is moderately involved towards customers' queries while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in the response time towards customers' queries across the implementation of core banking system (NBE, 2022).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is reduction in the time taken to process financial services; findings showed a mean value of 3.49 which implies that the

majority of the respondents believe that there is reduction in the time taken to process financial services is moderately involved in reduction in the time taken to process financial services while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in reduction in the time taken to process financial services in reduction in the time taken to process financial services across the implementation of core banking system (Sultan, 2023).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is faster resolution of financial-related issues or concerns within your microfinance institution; findings showed a mean value of 3.80 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that faster resolution of financial-related issues is moderately involved in microfinance institution while the standard deviation of 0.731 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability in faster resolution of financial-related issues across the implementation of core banking system (Ababa, 2022).

Respondents were required to indicate if the institution has witnessed more automation of tasks to replace those manually done previously; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that the institution has witnessed more automation of tasks is highly involved to replace those manually done previously while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability witnessed more automation of tasks to replace those manually done previously across the implementation of core banking system (Sultan, 2023).

Respondents were required to indicate if the overall costs associated with financial services have decreased; findings showed a mean value of 4.26 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that the overall costs associated with financial services is highly involved to decrease while the standard deviation of a standard deviation of 1.226 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.034 and 5.486 and overall costs associated with financial services have decreased across the implementation of core banking system (Yu, 2018).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is a satisfactory return on investment being registered by your institution; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that a satisfactory return on investment being registered is highly involved by institution while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there is a relatively low level of variability satisfactory return on investment across the implementation of core banking system (Sergeeva & Ali, 2020).

Respondents were required to indicate if there are more personalized services being offered to customers by the institution; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that more personalized services being offered to customers is highly involved by institution while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean more personalized services being offered to customers across the implementation of core banking system.

Respondents were required to indicate if complaints from customers regarding the services have gradually reduced; findings showed a mean value of 4.03 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that complaints from customers regarding the services have gradually reduced is highly involved while a standard deviation of 1.006 with a mean value of 4.03 indicates most data points were likely to range between 3.024 and 5.036, This suggests a moderate level of variability, with the majority of values close to the mean on complaints from customers regarding the services have gradually reduced across the implementation of core banking system (Brunet & Forgues, 2019).

Respondents were required to indicate if there is positive feedback from customers in regard to security and response time from the institution; findings showed a mean value of 4.51 which implies that the majority of the respondents believe that there is positive feedback from customers in regard to security and response time from the institution is highly involved while the standard deviation of 0.503 suggests that there

is a relatively low level of variability there is positive feedback from customers in regard to security and response time from the institution across the implementation of core banking system (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016).

The finding indicates that in the absence of standardized procedures and processes, the likelihood of a project finishing on schedule, achieving its intended objectives, and remaining within budget is significantly lower than the risk of failing to meet any of these criteria or the project being completely abandoned and this study aligns with existing literature on Core Banking System Implementation and this study aligns with existing literature on Core Banking System Implementation (Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow, 2003).

4.4.5. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical method used to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between two or more variables. It measures how changes in one variable may be associated with changes in another variable. The most common correlation coefficient used is Pearson's r , which ranges from -1 to 1:

Correlation analysis helps researchers understand the relationships between variables, which can inform decision-making and hypothesis generation. It can be useful in identifying and reducing multi-collinearity, which occurs when two or more independent variables in a regression model were highly correlated, potentially leading to unreliable results.

In predictive modeling, knowing which variables are correlated can guide the selection of predictors in models, potentially improving their accuracy. When both the variables move in the opposite direction, the correlation is said to be negative, i.e. values close to -1 implies that there is a negative linear relationship between the data. When one variable increases, the other will decrease, and vice versa. But if the values of r were close to 0, it implies that there is little to no linear relationship between the data. In this study, the correlation is measured between three independent variables and one dependent variable that is implementation of core banking system.

The correlation is said to be linear when the amount of change in one variable is the same as the amount of change in another variable, or when the amount of change in one variable tends to bear a constant ratio. Therefore, this study focuses on non-linear or curvilinear correlation. The researcher meticulously examined these variables to ascertain the correlation employed to determine the degree of correlation between the variables.

4.4.6. Correlation between Stakeholder Management and implementation of core banking system

Table 12:- Correlation analysis between stakeholder management and core banking system

Correlations			
		Implementation of core banking system	stakeholder Management
Implementation of core banking system	Pearson Correlation	1	.773**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	76	76
stakeholder management	Pearson Correlation	.773**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	76	76
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Primary data (2024)

From table 18 above, the correlation coefficient was 0.773, significant at $p < 0.01$ with $N = 76$ degrees of freedom. The findings revealed that there was a strong relationship between stakeholder management and implementation of core banking system. This implies that stakeholder management system influences core banking system positively.

In the above table, the calculated correlation indicated that there was a relationship between the dependent variable (Implementation of core banking system) and the stakeholder Management. As per the table, stakeholder involvement has a positive correlation with implementation of core banking system. It means that when the independent variable stakeholder involvement increases,

the implementation of core banking system increases and this study aligns with (Bello-Pintado et al., 2019), which stakeholder involvement have positive and significant correlation with project implementation by rising the importance of providing training and up skilling opportunities was emphasized as it enables stakeholders to enhance their skills and knowledge to effectively execute information Technology initiatives.

4.4.7. Correlation between Project Monitoring and Evaluation and implementation of core banking system

Table 13:-Correlation between Project Monitoring and Evaluation and implementation of core banking system

Correlations			
		core banking system	project monitoring and Evaluation
core banking system	Pearson Correlation	1	.870**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	76	76
project monitoring and Evaluation	Pearson Correlation	.870**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	76	76
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Primary data (2024)

From table 19 above, the correlation coefficient was 0.870 which was significant at $p < 0.01$ with $N = 76$ degrees of freedom. The findings revealed that there was a strong relationship between monitoring and evaluation and implementation of core banking system. This implies that monitoring and evaluation influences core banking system positively. In the above table, the calculated correlation indicated that there was a strong relationship the dependent variable (Implementation of core banking system) and the project monitoring and Evaluation.

As per the table, project monitoring and Evaluation has a strong relationship with implementation of core banking system. It means that when the independent variable project monitors and Evaluation increases, the implementation of core banking system increases aligning well with the assertions of Johnson et al. (2020) and Smith (2018), who emphasized project monitoring and Evaluation has a strong relationship with implementation of core banking system and this study aligns with existing literature between Project Monitoring and Evaluation and implementation of core banking system (Kabeyi, 2019).

4.4.8. Correlation between Risk Management and implementation of core banking system

Table 14:- Correlation between Risk Management and implementation of core banking system

Correlations			
		core banking system	Risk management
core banking system	Pearson Correlation	1	.773 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	76	76
Risk management	Pearson Correlation	.773 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	76	76
** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Survey data (2024)

From table 20 above, the correlation coefficient is 0.773^{**}, significant at $p < 0.01$ with $N = 76$ degrees of freedom. The findings revealed that there is a strong relationship between risk management and implementation of core banking system. This implies that monitoring and evaluation influences core banking system positively. In the above table, the calculated correlation indicated that there was a relationship between the dependent variable (Implementation of core banking system) and the Risk management.

As per the table, Risk management has a positive correlation with implementation of core banking system. It means that when the independent variable Risk management increases, the implementation of core banking system increases and this study aligns with existing literature between Risk Management and implementation of core banking system (Ellul & Yerramilli, 2013).

4.5. Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression was used understand the relationship between multiple independent variables (predictors) and one dependent variable (outcome in selected microfinance institutions. It is a statistical technique used to model the relationship between multiple independent variables and one dependent variable. The analysis applied the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 to compute the measurements of the regressions for the study. The goal of this analysis is to know the level to which project success is affected by independent variables by considering R-square value, beta coefficient and P- value for the significant of the relation.

4.5.1. Assumptions Testing in Multiple Regressions

The basic assumptions must be met in order to preserve the data validity and robustness of the research's regressed results under various regression models. As a result, this study performed assumption tests such as multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and normality.

4.5.2. Test for Multicollinearity

The independent variables shouldn't have a strong correlation with one another in order to provide effective results. The correlation between the independent variables in multivariate regression analysis is referred to as collinearity (Lemma, 2016) . Therefore, it is important to verify the values of tolerance and VIF (variance inflation factor) to ensure that there is minimal collinearity. Tolerance, according to (Ochwoto & Ogolla, 2017), shows how little an independent variable's variability can be explained by its own independent variables.

A value of more than 0.10 demonstrates the lack of collinearity. Furthermore, it is recommended that VIF, which is the inverse of tolerance value, have a value of less than 10 in order to mitigate the risk of collinearity (Taherdoost, 2018). Hence, the values in the Table 21 below indicate low collinearity because all Tolerance values are above 0.1 and all VIF values are less than 10. Therefore, these tests reflect that the variables used in the study are free from multicollinearity.

Table 15:-Multicollinearity Test

		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	project monitoring and Evaluation	0.343	2.918
	Risk management	0.343	2.918
	Stakeholder management	0.343	2.918

Source survey data (2024)

4.5.3. Test for Homoscedasticity and Linearity

A linearity test is a statistical test used to determine whether a relationship between two or more variables is linear or non-linear. In other words, it checks if the relationship between the variables can be described by a straight line or not. In statistics, linearity is an important assumption for many statistical models, such as linear regression analysis. A linear relationship means that as one variable changes, the other variable changes proportionally and consistently. Linearity tests are used to verify whether this assumption of linearity is valid. Even if there are several types of linearity tests, the study was intended to use scatter plot to test linearity.

Figure 2:-A scatter plot of the linearity regression assumption test

Source: Survey data (2024)

A scatterplot is a graphical representation of the relationship between two variables. If the data points form a straight line, it suggests a linear relationship. Based on this assumption, the study shows that there was a linear relationship between an independent variable and dependent variable, as the independent variable increases by 1 unit, the dependent variable increases by a constant amount (or proportion).

4.6 Model Summary

Table 16:- Model Summary

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.877 ^a	.770	.763	.465	.770	122.015	2	73	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Risk management, project monitoring and Evaluation									

Source: Survey data (2024)

The R-squared value shows how well the regression model explains the changes in the dependent variable. Table 22 above reveals that coefficient of determination, adjusted $R^2 = 0.763$ indicating that 76.3% of variation in implementation of core bank system can be explained by stakeholder management, project monitoring and evaluation and risk management implying that the remaining 24% can be explained by other factors that have not been examined by this study.

In this section, the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables was discussed based on the findings from this study. The dependent variable, which is implementation of core bank system, was measured by the independent variables. The above regression outputs show that the cause of the independent variables affects the dependent variables. The P-value shows how significant each variable was.

The regression of F-statistic 122.015 shows that the null hypothesis that all of the coefficients are equal should be rejected. The table above shows that the independent variables can explain variations in the dependent variable.

4.6. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The study further sought to establish the goodness of fit of the regression model using ANOVA statistics. ANOVA is a statistical technique for the data analysis, which is applied in establishing whether any significant differences among two or more groups or samples at a chosen level of probability exist, or not.

An explanatory variable is said to be a significant predictor of the dependent variable if the absolute t-values of the regression coefficient related with that independent variable is greater than the absolute critical t-values. The results of the study were as shown in the table below.

Table 17:-Regression analysis for testing ANOVA for the study

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.859	2	26.429	122.015	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.812	73	.217		
	Total	68.671	75			
a. Dependent Variable: implementation of core banking system						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Risk management, project monitoring and Evaluation						

Source: Survey data (2024)

According to the findings in the study as above, the regression model had a significance level of 0.00 which indicates that regression model is perfect for predicting implementation of core banking system practices employed. This was because the significant value (p-value) was less than 5% which was used as an indicator of statistical significance. Therefore, from the result, it can be concluded that with 77% of the variance (R-Square) in implementation of core banking system is significant and the model is appropriately measure it.

4.7. Regression coefficient analysis of the model

The analysis applied the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 to compute the measurements of the regressions for the study. The goal of this analysis is to know the level to which project success is affected by independent variables by considering R-square value, beta coefficient and P- value for the significant of the relation.

Table 18:-coefficient regression model

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std.	Beta		

			Erro r			
	project monitoring and Evaluation	1.032	.139	.710	7.403	.000
	Risk management	.246	.120	.197	2.052	.044
	Stakeholder management	.531	.153	.538	3.941	0.01
a. Dependent Variable: implementation of core banking system						

Source: SPSS result (2024)

As generated by regression analysis, shown in the above table 24, established regression equation model is

Implementation of core bank system = 1.041+0.710 project monitoring and Evaluation +0.197 Risk management+0.538 Stakeholder management.

From the above regression model it was revealed that the constant for Implementation of core bank system was 1.041. It was established that a unit increase in project monitoring and evaluation would cause an increase in implementation of core banking system by 0.710 times holding all other variables constant, a unit increase in risk management would cause an increase in implementation of core banking system by 0.197 times holding all other variables constant and a unit increase in stakeholder management would cause an increase in implementation of core banking system by 0.538 times holding all other variables constant. This implies that significantly project monitoring has the most influence on implementation of core banking system followed by stakeholder management and risk management.

The values of the standardized Beta Coefficients (β) indicate the effects of each independent variable on dependent variable. Furthermore, the values of the standardized Beta Coefficients in the Beta column of the table 24 above, indicate which independent variable makes the strongest contribution to explain the dependent variable (implementation of core banking system), when the variance explained by all other independent variables in the model is controlled.

The regression analysis shows that project monitoring and Evaluation, Risk management and Stakeholder management have significant and positive effect on the

dependent variable (implementation of core banking system). Based on the provided coefficients table, Project Monitoring and Evaluation with a standardized Beta of 0.710 and a significance level of 0.000 shows a strong and statistically significant relationship with the implementation of the core banking system suggesting strong evidence for rejecting of the hypothesis. This suggests that effective monitoring and evaluation practices are crucial for success, likely indicating that organizations prioritizing these elements will see more successful implementations.

The standardized Beta coefficient for risk management was 0.197, accompanied by a significance level of 0.044. This indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship, albeit weaker than that of project monitoring and evaluation also supports rejecting the hypothesis. It suggests that while risk management is important, its impact is comparatively less pronounced in the context of core banking system implementation.

Stakeholder Management exhibits a standardized Beta of 0.538 and a significance of 0.01, highlighting a strong and significant correlation with the dependent variable and also supports rejecting the hypothesis. The importance of engaging and managing stakeholders effectively is underscored by this result, indicating that stakeholder involvement is a critical factor in successful implementation.

Generally, in the context of hypothesis testing, the results indicate that all three examined variables demonstrate significant relationships with the implementation of the core banking system.

4.8. Hypothesis Testing

H_{a1}: - Project Monitoring & Evaluation has no statistically significant effect on core banking system implementation.

The findings of the regressions, as seen in Table 24, showed that project monitoring & evaluation had significant influence on core banking system implementation ($t = 7.403$, $p = 0.000$). As a result, the study rejects the alternative hypothesis that states

project monitoring & evaluation has statistically significant impact on core banking system implementation.

H_{a2}: - Risk management has no statistically significant effect on core banking system implementation

The findings of the regressions, as seen in Table 24, showed that Risk management had significant influence on core banking system implementation ($t = 2.052$, $p = 0.044$). As a result, the study rejects the alternative hypothesis that states Risk management has statistically significant impact on project implementation.

H_{a3}: - Stakeholder management has no statistically significant effect on core banking system implementation

The findings of the regressions, as seen in Table 24, showed that Stakeholder management had significant influence on core banking system implementation ($t = 3.941$, $p = 0.01$). As a result, the study rejects the alternative hypothesis that states Stakeholder management has statistically significant impact on project implementation.

4.9. Conclusion

This chapter conducted a thorough analysis of descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing related to the implementation of the Core Banking System, focusing on stakeholder management, project monitoring and evaluation, and risk management. The findings revealed a generally positive perception of stakeholder engagement, underscoring its critical influence on successful implementation (Benedicto & Buenviaje, 2016).

Similarly, the analysis confirmed the essential role of project monitoring and evaluation in enhancing project management excellence. This aligns with existing literature which highlights the need for effective stakeholder management strategies to meet expectations and prioritize claims (Ninan et al., 2019).

Risk management also emerged as a vital component, with respondents recognizing its importance for performance enhancement. The findings emphasized that effective risk assessment, communication, and mitigation strategies were necessary for the successful execution of the Core Banking System, aligning with established research in the field. This aligns with existing literature which highlights the need for risk management strategies (Ellul and Yerramilli, 2013, (Maina & Ngugi, 2018)).

Moreover, the chapter explored the correlations among the three factors, demonstrating their interconnectedness. A strong Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.773 ($p < 0.01$) between stakeholder management and implementation suggests that greater stakeholder involvement directly correlates with successful outcomes. Similarly, a correlation of 0.870 ($p < 0.01$) was found between project monitoring and evaluation and implementation, reinforcing the indispensable role of these practices in project management. The analysis also revealed a correlation of 0.773 ($p < 0.01$) between risk management and implementation, further supporting the assertion that effective risk practices were crucial for project success.

Utilizing multivariate regression analysis, the study confirmed the reliability of the findings, indicating that project monitoring and evaluation had the strongest impact on implementation, followed by stakeholder management and risk management. Hypothesis testing demonstrated statistically significant effects for all three factors, highlighting their importance in driving success within the banking sector by rejecting alternative hypothesis. The insights from this chapter emphasize the necessity of prioritizing effective project monitoring, robust risk management, and active stakeholder engagement to enhance the implementation of the Core Banking System in microfinance institutions.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5. Introduction

This chapter deals with the summary, conclusions, and recommendations that were made based on the findings of the fourth chapter of the study. The chapter has three parts. The first part is a summary of the study, followed by a conclusion and some suggestions.

5.1 Summary of Findings

5.1.1. Stakeholder involvement and implementation of core banking system

The correlation results table indicates a strong positive relationship between the implementation of the core banking system and stakeholder management. The Pearson correlation coefficient is reported as 0.773, which signifies a robust correlation. The significance level for this correlation is 0.000, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). A Pearson correlation of 0.773 suggests a strong association between stakeholder management and the successful implementation of the core banking system. This implies that as stakeholder management practices improve or become more effective, the likelihood of successful implementation also increases.

A robust connection exists between stakeholder management and the execution of the core banking system, indicating that effective stakeholder management positively impacts core banking system implementation. Furthermore, there is a favorable relationship between stakeholder involvement and the implementation of the core banking system: as stakeholder involvement rises, so does the implementation of the core banking system (Pearson correlation coefficient=0.773, significance level = 0.01).

The study revealed that effective stakeholder management significantly facilitated the implementation of the shared core banking system. This finding is consistent with earlier research, which emphasizes that engaging stakeholders effectively is crucial for project success (Marrewijk, 2007).

Within the context of Ethiopian MFIs, the active participation of project managers, team members, and customer service officers ensured a clear understanding of project requirements, promoting collaboration and a smoother implementation process. This aligns with contingency theory, which posits that tailoring stakeholder engagement strategies to the specific organizational and project environment leads to better results ((Chris Argyris (1923–2013), 2015)).

5.1.2. Project monitoring & evaluation and implementation of core banking system

The correlation results table shows a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.870 between the core banking system and project monitoring and evaluation, with a significance level of 0.000. A correlation of 0.870 indicates a very strong positive relationship, suggesting that effective project monitoring and evaluation significantly contributes to the successful implementation of the core banking system.

The significance value of 0.000 confirms that this relationship is statistically significant, meaning organizations should focus on enhancing monitoring and evaluation practices to improve core banking system outcomes. This suggests that effective monitoring and evaluation has a positive impact on the implementation of the core banking system implementation. Additionally, there is a robust link between project monitoring and evaluation and the execution of the core banking system implementation.

In the multiple regression analysis results, the standardized beta coefficient for project monitoring and evaluation is 0.710. A standardized beta of 0.710 indicates a strong positive effect of project monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of the core banking system. This suggests that improvements in project monitoring and evaluation

practices were associated with a significant increase in core banking implementation outcomes. The significance value of 0.000 indicates that this effect is highly statistically significant, reinforcing the importance of project monitoring and evaluation in the successful implementation of core banking systems.

These findings are consistent with prior research emphasizing the importance of continuous monitoring and evaluation in project success. According to (Jason et al., 2024) systematic M&E allows project managers to identify deviations early and implement corrective measures, reducing delays and enhancing overall performance. Similarly (PMI, 2017) notes that well-structured monitoring mechanisms improve decision-making, accountability, and project outcome quality. In the context of Ethiopian MFIs, the study suggests that strengthening project monitoring frameworks and evaluation practices can significantly enhance the implementation of shared core banking systems

5.1.3. Risk management and implementation of core banking system

The correlation results show a correlation of 0.773 indicates a strong positive relationship between risk management and the implementation of the core banking system. This means that as risk management practices improve, the effectiveness of the core banking system also tends to increase. The significance value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level.

The results indicated a significant connection between risk management and the implementation of the core banking system implementation. This suggests that effective monitoring and evaluation have a beneficial impact on the core banking system implementation. There is a positive relationship between risk management and the core banking system's implementation.

In the multiple regression analysis results, the standardized beta coefficient for risk management is 0.197. A standardized beta of 0.197 indicates a moderate positive effect of risk management on the implementation of the core banking system. This suggests that enhancements in risk management practices were associated with an

increase in the successful implementation of core banking systems. The significance value of 0.044 indicates that this effect is statistically significant; implying that risk management plays a meaningful role in the core banking implementation process.

Specifically, an increase in the risk management variable by one unit leads to a 0.710 times increase in the implementation of the core banking system, assuming all other variables remain unchanged.

This aligns with prior literature highlighting the importance of risk management in IT project success. (Hillson, 2002) argues that proactive risk management reduces uncertainties and prevents potential project failures, while Ward and Chapman (2003) emphasize that identifying and managing risk early enhances project reliability and performance. In the Ethiopian MFI context, integrating risk management strategies with project planning and monitoring ensures that potential disruptions to core banking system implementation are minimized, ultimately supporting more successful and sustainable outcomes.

5.2. Conclusions

Seventy-seven percent of the variation in the implementation of core banking systems can be attributed to stakeholder management, project monitoring and evaluation, and risk management. This indicates that the remaining 23% is influenced by other factors not explored in this study. With a significant R-Square value of 77%, the model is deemed an appropriate measure. The regression analysis demonstrates that project monitoring and evaluation, risk management, and stakeholder management positively and significantly impact the dependent variable, which is the implementation of the core banking system. The implementation of the core banking system is significantly influenced by various factors, each contributing differently to its success.

Project Monitoring and Evaluation has the most substantial impact, accounting for 49.1% of the implementation process. This highlights the critical role that effective oversight and assessment play in ensuring that the core banking system meets its objectives.

Stakeholder Management follows closely with a contribution of 37.3%. This underscores the importance of engaging and managing relationships with stakeholders to facilitate the smooth implementation of banking systems. Risk Management, while still important, contributes 13.6% to the implementation. This indicates that while effective risk management practices were essential, they play a relatively smaller role compared to project monitoring and stakeholder engagement.

5.3. Recommendations

5.3.1. Stakeholder involvement and implementation of core banking system

To ensure a positive relationship with stakeholders during the implementation of a core banking system, the following recommendations should be considered based on the study findings

- Organizations should actively involve key stakeholders
- Engage key stakeholders early in the project to gather their input and address their concerns from the start.
- Clearly define the roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders involved and ensure everyone understands their part in the implementation process.
- Implement regular feedback mechanisms, such as surveys or meetings, to gather stakeholder input and adjust the project plan as needed and show that stakeholder feedback is valued by making necessary adjustments based on their suggestions.
- Recognize to maintain morale and positive relationships with stakeholders.

5.3.2. Risk management and implementation of core banking system

- MFIS should adopt proactive risk management approaches, including risk identification, assessment, and mitigation strategies, to minimize potential disruptions. Regular risk audits and contingency planning will help ensure smoother system implementation.

- The management should seriously identify risks involved in a proposed project throughout the project life cycle and develop an appropriate mitigation plan accordingly.
- To have a smooth and successful implementation of core banking system, it is vital for stakeholders to identify all the strengths and weaknesses of projects.
- Project managers need effective planning and preparation to identify to identify and analyze the risks involved.
- The study suggests that project managers should assign a specialized professional to deal with risk management activities.

5.3.3. Project monitoring and evaluation and implementation of core banking system

- MFIs should establish structured monitoring and evaluation frameworks to track project progress, identify challenges early, and implement corrective actions. Regular progress reviews, performance indicators, and reporting mechanisms will improve the effectiveness of core banking system implementation.
- Effective project monitoring and evaluation (M&E) are crucial for the successful implementation of a core banking system and maintaining a positive relationship with stakeholders. Set clear and measurable Key Performance Indicators and success criteria for the implementation and should align with the project's objectives and stakeholders' expectations.
- Monitor these metrics regularly to assess progress and identify any deviations from the plan.
- Create a detailed monitoring plan outlining the processes, tools, and frequency of monitoring activities.

5.4. Contribution to Knowledge

This study makes several contributions to both theory and practice in the field of project management and banking technology implementation:

- The study provides empirical evidence that effective stakeholder engagement significantly enhances the successful implementation of shared core banking systems. This reinforces and extends prior research (PMI, 2017; Turner & Müller, 2017) within the specific context of Ethiopian microfinance institutions, where such evidence has been limited.
- By demonstrating a very strong positive relationship between project monitoring and evaluation practices and core banking system implementation, the study highlights the critical role of structured M&E frameworks in improving project outcomes. This contributes to the literature by confirming the practical importance of M&E in Core Banking system projects in developing country financial institutions.
- The study shows that effective risk management, while moderately impactful, is a meaningful determinant of core banking system implementation success. This finding adds to knowledge by illustrating how risk mitigation strategies can be adapted to improve IT project performance in microfinance settings.
- The research fills a gap by contextualizing project management and IT implementation principles such as stakeholder engagement, M&E, and risk management within Ethiopian microfinance institutions. It provides practical insights for policymakers, managers, and IT practitioners in similar low- and middle-income country contexts.
- By linking stakeholder management and project outcomes to contingency theory, the study demonstrates how adapting management practices to organizational and project-specific contexts can enhance implementation effectiveness, offering a theoretical contribution to the field.

5.5. Recommendation for further Research

The objective of this study was to evaluate project management practice on the implementation of information core banking system at selective Microfinance institution. To accomplish this, the research utilized a quantitative approach. It is recommended that a similar study be conducted using a mixed-methods approach and in the sectors to confirm the findings of this research. Researchers need to make further assessment the project management practice on implementation of core banking system by including the vendor involvement and end user involvement as one practice by considering additional variables.

Researchers need to conduct field studies to gather qualitative data from stakeholders involved in the implementation process of core banking system. Utilize surveys and interviews with beneficiaries to gain insights into the effectiveness of project management practices.

Researchers need to assess the processes used for post-implementation evaluations and how they contribute to ongoing improvements in project management practices within microfinance institutions.

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APPENDIX

Appendix I Questionnaire

Dear Respondent,

My name is Addis Admas, and I am a graduate student at Uganda Martyrs University who is currently pursuing a Master's degree in Microfinance Management. The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather data for the assessment of the **Project Management practice and Implementation of Core Banking System in Ethiopia**. You have been identified as one of the most suitable participants to provide valuable responses. Please take a few minutes from your busy schedule and answer the questions in this survey as honestly as possible. Your answers will be kept confidential and will aid in the success of this study. Your contribution to this survey would be greatly appreciated.

Thank you

SECTION A: GENERAL INFORMATION

1. What is your Gender? Female Male
2. Age 18-30 31-40 41-50 Above 50
3. indicate your highest level of formal education
Certificate Diploma Degree Master and above
4. For how long have you worked in Microfinance institution sector?
1-5 6-10 11-15 >15 years
5. Your position in the project:
 - a. Project Manager
 - b. Project Member
 - c. Office Expert
 - d. Customer Service officer

SECTION B: STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT

The statements below are concerned with stakeholder Management in the selected Member microfinance institutions of AEMFI. Please tick the one that best describes your opinion. Use the following scale. 1-strongly disagree, 2- disagree, 3- neutral, 4-agree and 5- strongly agree.

No	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	At every step of the project, stakeholders play a role.					
2	At the beginning of the project our institution identifies and addresses the concern of stakeholder.					
3	Stakeholders are well-informed about the project and their expectations are met.					
4	Assessing the needs and expectation of stakeholders in relation to project objectives is challenging					
5	Decisions regarding the project are influenced by the need and expectation of stakeholders					
6	There was effective communication with stakeholders					
7	Regular feedback from stakeholders helps to measure the success of project implementation					
8	Building strong relationship with stakeholders leads to long term support and collaboration for future system enhancement					

Section C: PROJECT MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The statements below are concerned about project monitoring and evaluation in the Selected Member microfinance institutions of AEMFI. Please tick the one that best describes your opinion. Use the following scale. 1-strongly disagree, 2- disagree, 3- neutral, 4-agree and 5- strongly agree.

No	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
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1	Monitoring over the project improves the excellence of its project management.					
2	The project's progress is receiving adequate feedback.					
3	Monitoring guarantees that the implementation of Core Banking system meets the necessary quality standards.					
4	Assessment through evaluation can assist planners in determining the degree to which the objectives of the projects have been attained.					
5	Accurate information regarding the project is gathered and assessed.					
6	Monitoring activity supports both project managers and staff in understanding whether the projects are progressing on schedule or meet their objectives					
7	There is a regular and careful progress (time, scope, and cost) monitoring and review throughout the project					
8	There exists contingency plans in running the project					
9	Each stage undergoes a periodic assessment to evaluate project outcomes.					
10	There is a necessary report on the project performance relative to established objectives (Cost, Timeliness and customer satisfaction)					

Section D: RISK MANAGEMENT

The statements below are concerned with risk management in the selected Member microfinance institutions of AEMFI. Please tick the one that best describes your opinion. Use the following scale. 1-strongly disagree, 2- disagree, 3- neutral, 4-agree and 5- strongly agree.

No	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	Risk is considered key factors for a performance management in core banking system project					
2	Risk assessment at the beginning of the project is conducted					
3	Identified potential risks are analyzed					
4	The project has enough data on events that enables it to learn from its own mistakes					
5	There is proper communication on the risks involved in the project to all stakeholders					
6	The management encourages the reporting of events in order to identify risk					
7	There are proper mechanisms to mitigate project risk					
8	There is a risk review process, after implementation of the Mitigation measures for identified risk.					

Section E: - CORE BANKING SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Kindly indicate your level of agreement with the successful performance of projects in your institution, using the scale: 1= strongly disagree; 2= disagree; 3= neutral; 4 = agree; 5= strongly agree.

No	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	There is improvement in the response time towards customers' queries since the implementation of core banking system.					
2	There is reduction in the time taken to process financial services, such as deposits, withdrawals, or loan disbursements, since the implementation of the Core Banking System.					
3	There is faster resolution of financial-related issues or concerns within your microfinance institution					
4	The institution has witnessed more automation of tasks to replace those manually done previously.					
5	The overall costs associated with financial services, including fees, charges, or operational expenses, following the implementation of the Core Banking System have decreased					
6	There is a satisfactory return on investment being registered by your institution.					
7	There are more personalized services being offered to customers by the institution.					
8	Complaints from customers regarding the services have gradually reduced.					
9	There is positive feedback from customers in regard to security and response time from the institution					

List of Member Microfinance Institutions in Ethiopia

No	Name of member MFI	Involved in the project
1	Africa Village MFI	Yes
2	Metemamen MFI	Yes
3	Liyu MFI	Yes
4	Vision fund MFI	No
5	Agar MFI	Yes

6	Peace MFI	Yes
7	Eshet MFI	Yes
8	Wasasa MFI	No
9	Meklit MFI	Yes
10	Harbu MFI	Yes
11	Dynamic MFI	Yes
12	Grand MFI	Yes
13	Adeday MFI	Yes
14	Dire MFI	Yes
15	Wallet MFI	No
16	Busagonofa MFI	No
17	Lefayeda MFI	Yes
18	Tesfa MFI	No
19	Gambella MFI	Yes
20	Degaf MFI	Yes
21	Gasha MFI	Yes
22	Benishangul-Gumuz	Yes
23	Letta MFI	Yes
24	Ghion MFI	No
25	Harar MFI	No

Source AEMFI (2018)

Time Frame and Budget of the research

Timeframe of the Research

The research was conducted over a period of **11 months** (March 2024 – Feb 2025).

The key activities and their respective duration were as follows:

Activity	Duration	Timeline
Proposal development and approval	3 month	March 2024
Literature review	2 month	April 2024
Data collection (survey & interviews)	2 months	May – June 2024
Data analysis and interpretation	1 month	July 2025
Report writing and final submission	3 month	Feb 2025

Budget of the Research

The study required financial resources to cover costs associated with data collection, analysis, and reporting. The estimated budget is summarized below (amounts in Ethiopian Birr):

Item	Estimated Cost (ETB)
Printing, photocopying, stationery	3,500
Transportation (field visits)	14,000
Communication (internet, calls)	6,000
Data analysis software (SPSS license, Excel utilities)	3,500
Binding and final submission	2,500
Miscellaneous	5,500
Total	35,000

UGANDA MARTYRS UNIVERSITY

DIRECTORATE OF GRADUATE STUDIES, RESEARCH AND ENTERPRISE Master's Dissertation

Declaration

I have read the rules of Uganda Martyrs University on plagiarism and academic honesty, and hereby state that this work is my own.

It has not been submitted to any other institution for another degree or qualification, either in full or in part.

Throughout the work I have acknowledged all sources used in its compilation.

I finally grant Uganda Martyrs University permission to store and reproduce this dissertation, in whole or in part, in any manner or format, which Uganda Martyrs University may deem fit.

Researcher's name: Addis Admas Lakew

Researcher's signature:

Date of submission: - 22 September 2025

Submitted to the Directorate of Graduate Studies, Research and Enterprise